

Stroke Audit Machine Learning (SAMueL-2)

Michael Allen^{*1,2}, Kerry Pearn^{1,2}, Rachel Jarvie¹, Anna Laws¹, Julia Frost¹, Leon Farmer¹, Peter McMeekin³, Catherine Pope⁴, Iain Lang¹, Keira Pratt-Boyden¹, Richard Everson¹, and Martin James^{1,5}

¹University of Exeter Medical School

²NIHR South West Peninsula Applied Research Collaboration (ARC)

³Northumbria University

⁴University of Oxford

⁵Royal Devon University Healthcare NHS Foundation Trust

*Corresponding author: m.allen@exeter.ac.uk

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Abstract

Background

Use of thrombolysis to treat emergency stroke patients varies considerably between hospitals. Previous work has shown that the majority of this variation comes from between-hospital decision-making on which patients should receive thrombolysis.

Key objectives

- Use qualitative methodologies to ask *"What should a machine-learning model based on national audit data look like, do, and deliver, to optimise improvement and reduce unwarranted variation, in thrombolysis?"*
- Use explainable machine learning to investigate what affects whether a patient receives thrombolysis or not, and what affect that thrombolysis has on patient outcome. Use *prototype patients* to further illustrate the relationship between patient features, expected use of thrombolysis, and expected patient outcomes.
- Incorporate health economics in patient outcome modelling.
- Model patient flow from stroke onset to disability at discharge.

Methods

- **Co-production and qualitative research** used observations, meetings, semi-structured interviews, and review of NHS documentation.
- **Thrombolysis decisions and patient outcomes** were predicted using XGBoost machine learning models, employing Shapley values to explain individual feature contributions.
- Scenarios of **patient flow through the emergency stroke pathway** was modelled with Monte-Carlo simulation, and a mathematical model of outcome based on clinical trial results.

Results

- **Qualitative insights** found optimism among participants about using SAMueL-2 technology to standardise thrombolysis practices, being especially beneficial for less experienced clinicians for training and case review. It identified the importance to reassure adopters about the integrity of modelling based on SSNAP, and that emergency department physicians have less confidence about the evidence base for thrombolysis.
- **Key factors affecting thrombolysis use** in ischaemic stroke are arrival-to-scan time, stroke severity, pre-stroke disability, and the hospital attended. After adjusting for other patient features, a 13-fold variability in thrombolysis odds was observed between-hospitals.
- **Key factors affecting outcome** after stroke are pre-stroke disability, stroke severity, age, and use/time of thrombolysis. Machine learning demonstrated that thrombolysis was having at least the expected clinical benefit as predicted by the clinical trials. Thrombolysis was predicted to add an average of 0.26 QALYs per patient treated. Hospitals with higher thrombolysis use are predicted to be generating better patient outcomes.
- Combining **changes to processes and decision-making** could increase thrombolysis use from 13% to 20% among patients arriving by ambulance. Accelerating pathway speed positively influenced outcomes more than thrombolysis rates. A web tool was developed for stroke team-level data interrogation.

Conclusions

Using large-scale observational data and machine learning, thrombolysis, in real world use, was found to have at least as much benefit as predicted by the thrombolysis clinical trial meta-analysis. Both qualitative research and machine learning revealed significant between-hospital variation in which patients receive thrombolysis, which is leading to significant between-hospital variation in thrombolysis use and outcomes. Machine learning revealed that who will benefit from thrombolysis is patient-specific, and not easily captured in a simple medicine use label, but we found overall that stroke teams with a higher willingness to use thrombolysis are predicted to be generating better patient outcomes at a population level.

Plain Language Summary

What is the problem? Use of clot-busting treatment (*‘thrombolysis’*) in stroke varies a great deal between hospitals.

What did we know? We knew that the largest cause of this variation was in how doctors decide which patients are suitable for thrombolysis. Some doctors are worried that the risk from this treatment can outweigh the benefits, and that use of this treatment in the real world won’t have the same benefit that was predicted by the clinical trials.

What did we not know? We did not know (1) how the variation in use of thrombolysis was affecting patient outcomes, (2) what it was about the patients that doctors considered when making decisions, (3) what most affected patient outcome, (4) what doctors would think of using *machine learning* (where a computer learns patterns in data) to help understand answers to these questions.

What did we do? We used machine learning to learn which patients different hospitals would give thrombolysis to, and to learn which patients would likely have a better outcome if this treatment was used.

What did we find out? We found out that thrombolysis was at least as effective in real use as clinical trials predicted, and that hospitals choosing to use it more are very likely saving more lives and reducing disability from stroke. We now understand what doctors look at when deciding to use it or not, and what affects patient outcomes. We found that speeding up giving this treatment would increase the number of people who would receive it, and by everyone receiving it sooner would mean they would each benefit more from it. We now understand that hospitals are making a delicate treatment decision between ‘Miss no benefit’ and ‘Do no harm’, and that many factors contribute to making this complex decision correctly. We found that doctors were interested in our work, but they need to be convinced our machine learning is right. We are hopeful that our results will give doctors greater confidence to use this treatment more often, and to always give it as fast as possible.

1 Introduction

Stroke remains one of the top three global causes of death and disability⁶. Despite reductions in age-standardised rates of stroke, ageing populations are driving an increase in the absolute number of strokes⁶. Across Europe, in 2017, stroke was found to cost healthcare systems €27 billion, or 1.7% of health expenditure⁷. Thrombolysis with recombinant tissue plasminogen activator, can significantly reduce disability after ischaemic stroke, so long as it is given in the first few hours after stroke onset⁸. Despite thrombolysis being of proven benefit in ischaemic stroke, use of thrombolysis varies significantly both between and within European countries⁹. In England and Wales the national stroke audit reported that in 2021/22, 20 years on from the original European Medicines Agency licensing of alteplase for thrombolysis in acute ischaemic stroke, thrombolysis rates for emergency stroke admissions varied from just 1% to 28% between hospitals¹⁰, with a median rate of 10.4% and an inter-quartile range of 8%-13%, against a 2019 NHS England long term plan that 20% of patients of emergency stroke admissions should be receiving thrombolysis¹¹.

The NHS plan for improving stroke care also sets a target that patients should receive thrombolysis within 60 minutes of arrival, but ideally within 20 minutes (12). Whilst this speed of thrombolysis, called door-to-needle time, provides an ambitious target, it has been shown to be achievable as Helsinki University Central Hospital has reported a median door-to-needle time of 20 minutes, with 94% of patients treated within 60 minutes¹².

Studies have shown that reasons for low and varying thrombolysis rates are multi-factorial. Reasons include late presentation⁹, lack of expertise⁹ or lack of clear protocols or training¹³, delayed access to specialists¹⁴, and poor triage by ambulance or emergency department staff¹³. For many factors, the establishment of primary stroke centres has been suggested to improve the emergency care of patients with stroke and reduce barriers to thrombolysis¹³, with a centralised model of primary stroke centres leading to increased likelihood of thrombolysis^{15;16;17}.

In addition to organisational factors, clinicians can have varying attitudes to which patients are suitable candidates for thrombolysis. In a discrete choice experiment¹⁸, 138 clinicians considered hypothetical patient vignettes, and responded as to whether they would give the patients thrombolysis. The authors concluded that there was considerable heterogeneity among respondents in their thrombolysis decision-making. Areas of difference were around whether to give thrombolysis to mild strokes, to older patients beyond 3 hours from stroke onset, and when there was pre-existing disability.

Based on national audit data from three years of emergency stroke admissions, we have previously built models of the emergency stroke pathway using clinical pathway simulation to examine the potential scale of the effect of changing two aspects of the stroke pathway performance (1. the in-hospital process speeds, and 2. the proportion of patients with a determined stroke onset time), and using machine learning to examine the effect of replicating clinical decision-making around thrombolysis from higher thrombolysing hospitals to lower thrombolysing hospitals^{19;20}. The machine learning model learned whether any particular patient would receive thrombolysis in any particular emergency stroke centre. Using these models we found that it would be credible to target an increase in average thrombolysis in England and Wales, from 11% to 18%, but that each hospital should have its own target, reflecting differences in local populations. We found that the largest increase in thrombolysis use would come from replicating thrombolysis decision-making practice from higher to lower thrombolysing hospitals. Two other important factors influencing thrombolysis rates were determination of stroke onset time in some hospitals, and improving the speed of the in-hospital thrombolysis pathway.

In our previous work we established that we could predict the use of thrombolysis in patients arriving within 4 hours of known stroke onset with 84.3% accuracy²⁰. We could then ask the question "What if this patient attended another hospital - would they likely be given thrombolysis?" As this was a *'black-box'* decision-forest model we could not effectively explain the relationship between patient level data ('features') and their chance of receiving thrombolysis, or identify and explain the features which different hospitals would differ on. In that work we were also only predicting thrombolysis choice; we were not examining outcomes after stroke with and without thrombolysis, which left open the question of whether stroke teams with higher thrombolysis use were likely to be achieving better outcomes. Incorporating explainability of predictions, and predicting outcomes were therefore key objectives for the current study.

The specific objectives for the current study were as follows (Appendix section A2 reports on how these objectives were met):

1. **Co-production of project outputs with clinicians to promote acceptance and use for local quality improvement** by using qualitative research methodologies to ask "What should a machine-learning model based

on SSNAP data look like, do, and deliver if it is to optimise improvement, and reduce unwarranted variation, in thrombolysis?

- To generate empirically and theoretically informed knowledge about how thrombolysis is currently delivered, centred on physicians' views, understandings, and practices.
 - To learn more about how stroke physicians' and staff think and feel about or use SSNAP, and about the use of machine learning in improving clinical practice.
2. **Expansion of previous (SAMueL-1) modelling** to include: 1) outcome and adverse event prediction at patient-level, 2) inclusion of pre-hospital times in pathway model, 3) use of organisational factors (such as staffing) in predicting use of thrombolysis, and 4) piloting of a model that incorporates use of thrombectomy alongside thrombolysis.
 3. **Incorporation of health economic outcomes** (Quality Adjusted Life Years, QALYs): These will be adapted from other NIHR projects involving this team that have already developed health economic models for thrombolysis in acute ischaemic stroke.
 4. **Promote acceptance of the modelling by increased transparency and explainability**: 1) make use of Shapley values to show the contribution of individual features to the prediction that the model is making, 2) improved methods for clustering of patients to clarify patterns of differences in clinical decision-making between hospitals and to allow identification of 'similar hospitals' (by patient population) for comparison, 3) investigation of bias in model (e.g. accuracy analysis by patient subgroups), 4) generation of dashboards and other interrogative methods.
 5. **Generation of synthetic data and artificial patient vignettes**: 1) build on pilot work already performed for generating synthetic patient-level stroke data that may be shared freely and used for discussion of 'virtual' patients, 2) automatic generation of artificial clinical vignettes from real or synthetic SSNAP data.

2 Emergency stroke pathway under study

This project focused on use of thrombolysis and outcomes (with and without thrombolysis) at discharge from in-patient care. Figure 1 shows an overview of the process steps included in the modelling. All modelling data came from the national stroke registry for England, Wales and Northern Ireland, the Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP).

- *Stroke onset*: When known, SSNAP records the time of stroke onset.
- *Convey to hospital*: SSNAP records the time of arrival at hospital, and records whether the arrival was by ambulance or not. For some patients there is a breakdown of ambulance response times (time of call, time of ambulance arrival on scene, time of departure from scene, time of arrival at hospital).
- *Gather info & determine stroke onset time*: SSNAP records whether onset time was determined, and whether it was considered to be known *precisely* or was *a best estimate*. Other patient information is gathered (such as recording age, sex, the NIH Stroke Scale scores, estimation of pre-stroke disability, key medications being taken by the patient). This clinical information may be taken prior to and/or after head imaging, but we restricted information for modelling treatment decisions to that information available at the time of the decision.
- *Head scan*: Head imaging is essential to confirm stroke, and determine stroke type (ischaemic or hemorrhagic). SSNAP records whether head imaging was performed, and the time of imaging. For modelling work described here we did not request, and do not use, the mode of imaging; all modes should provide confirmation of stroke and should distinguish ischaemic and hemorrhagic stroke.
- *Decision to treat*: We model each stroke teams patterns of who they decide to treat with thrombolysis.
- *Thrombolysis (IVT)*: SSNAP records whether thrombolysis was given and the time of thrombolysis.
- *Disability at discharge*: SSNAP records modified Rankin Scale (mRS) at discharge from inpatient care. For about third of patients there is a follow-up measure at 6 months. In our modelling we use disability at discharge as (1)

data is essentially complete, and (2) this is the outcome most closely tied with the effect of thrombolysis, which is our focus of study in the described project.

Figure 1: An overview of the process steps included in the modelling.

Process flow was modelled by sampling from distributions of historic flow for each stroke team. Decision-making (choice of thrombolysis) was modelled with machine learning, learning which patients would likely be given thrombolysis at each stroke team. Outcomes were predicted using either mathematical models based on clinical trials (for the full pathway model), or clinical outcome machine learning models (for the more detailed analysis of differences in thrombolysis decision-making between teams).

2.1 Data

2.2 Data for modelling

Data was extracted from the Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP), the national stroke registry for England, Wales and Northern Ireland, for all patients with an out-of-hospital stroke onset for the full calendar years of 2016-2021. The registry contains patients admitted to all acutely-admitting hospitals, with a case ascertainment of over 90% when compared to administrative data (Hospital Episode Statistics). The total number of patients was 360,381, of whom 38.5% arrived within 4 hours of known stroke onset. Of those arriving within 4 hours of known stroke onset 90.4% arrived by ambulance (71.6% of those not arriving within 4 hours of known stroke onset arrived by ambulance).

The following data fields from SSNAP were used in the modelling:

- *Stroke team*: Stroke team attended (hospital identifier).
- *Age*: Age (as midpoint of 5 year age bands).
- *Sex*: Sex of patient.
- *Atrial fibrillation diagnosis*: Patient had a diagnosis of atrial fibrillation, either on arrival or diagnosed during admission.
- *Use of atrial fibrillation (AF) anticoagulants*: Use of prior anticoagulant for atrial fibrillation.
- *Onset known*: Whether onset was known, and if known whether it was considered to be known precisely or was a best estimate.
- *Onset during sleep*: Did stroke occur in sleep?
- *Onset-to-arrival time*: Time from onset of stroke to arrival at hospital (minutes), when known.
- *Prior disability level*: Estimated mRS score prior to stroke.
- *Stroke type*: Infarction/haemorrhage.
- *Stroke severity*: National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) score on arrival.
- *Arrival-to-scan time*: Time from arrival at hospital to scan (minutes), when known.
- *Scan-to-thrombolysis time*: Time from arrival at hospital to scan to treatment with thrombolysis (minutes), when given.
- *Disability on discharge*: mRS (0-6) on discharge, includes death (mRS 6) during admission.

Appendix sectionA1 provides descriptive statistics for patients across stroke teams. See sections 5 to 8 for further details on data used for each component of the modelling work.

2.2.1 Ethics

For modelling, as we were using anonymised secondary data, collected for national audit, individual consent is not required. SSNAP has approval under section 251 of the NHS Health and Social Care Act (2006) to collect patient level data on the first six months of patient care (ECC 6- 02(FT3)/2012), without requiring individual patient consent. Access to SSNAP data is managed by the UK Healthcare Quality Improvement Partnership (HQIP), with this project being approved by HQIP (HQIP303). More information on the use of patient data by SSNAP can be found at <https://www.strokeaudit.org/SupportFiles/Documents/Patient-area-documents/Fair-processingstatement-for-patients-v7-0.aspx>

As we are using anonymised secondary data, collected for national audit, used for service evaluation and improvement, no ethical approval is required (confirmed using the NHS Health Research Authority decision aid: <https://www.hra-decisiontools.org.uk/ethics/>).

2.3 Data for qualitative research

Qualitative research used a combination of ethnographic observations, interviews and documentary analysis. See section 4 for further details.

2.3.1 Ethics

For the qualitative study, NHS Health Research Authority (HRA) & Health and Care Research Wales (HCRW) approval was provided by the Essex Research Ethics Committee in August 2023 (IRAS 322303; REC reference 23/EE/0124).

3 Overview of project papers: Study overviews and key findings

3.1 Paper 1: Stroke physicians' and staff perspectives on machine learning to optimise thrombolysis decision making in stroke: a qualitative study.¹

Study type and population

Qualitative study: 184 hours of focused observation in three NHS Trusts in England. Observation of Integrated Stroke Delivery Networks (ISDNs) and other organisations with a strategic overview of stroke services. 20 participants from the three observation sites and five key informants from other sites took part in semi-structured interviews.

Key findings

- Participants were hopeful the SAMueL-2 technology could address variance in thrombolysis practice. It was seen as particularly suitable for junior clinicians, non-stroke specialists and at district general hospitals and offered value for training, reviewing clinical cases, and quality improvement.
- Given reservations expressed about the underpinning SSNAP data, it is important to reassure intended adopters about the integrity of modelling based on this data.
- Evidence indicated that emergency department physicians may have less confidence in the evidence base for thrombolysis.
- Perceived lack of funding and stroke workforce shortages may impede quality improvement and adoption of new technologies such as SAMueL-2

3.2 Paper 2: What would other emergency stroke teams do? Using explainable machine learning to understand variation in thrombolysis practice.²

Study type and population

Explainable machine learning model to study decision-to-treat with thrombolysis across 132 stroke teams. The model was based on 3 years of all emergency stroke arrivals to hospitals in England and Wales, arriving within 4 hours of stroke onset (88,928 patients).

Key findings

1. Thrombolysis use in patients arriving within 4 hours of known or estimated stroke onset ranged 7% to 49% between hospitals.
2. The odds of receiving thrombolysis reduced 9-fold over the first 120 minutes of arrival-to-scan time, varied 30-fold with stroke severity, reduced 3-fold with estimated rather than precise stroke onset time, reduced 6-fold with increasing pre-stroke disability, reduced 4-fold with onset during sleep, reduced 5-fold with use of anticoagulants, reduced 2-fold between 80 and 110 years of age, reduced 3-fold between 120 and 240 min of onset-to-arrival time and varied 13-fold between hospitals.
3. The majority of between-hospital variance was explained by the hospital, rather than by the differences in local patient populations.

3.3 Paper 3: Thrombolysis: Are the results from the clinical trial meta-analysis seen in real life outcomes? A machine learning study of the UK stroke registry.³

Study type and population

Explainable machine learning model to investigate clinical benefit of thrombolysis (in those patients who received thrombolysis), compared with clinical trials. The model was based on 6 years of emergency ischaemic stroke admissions that arrived at an acute stroke team in England and Wales by ambulance after their stroke onset, which did not go on to receive thrombectomy (168,347 patients). Includes 118 acute stroke hospitals (each with at least 250 stroke admissions and at least 10 thrombolysis procedures in the study period).

Key findings

- Thrombolysis was found to be associated with a statistically significant improvement in the odds of having a good outcome using any mRS threshold. Regression analysis predicted a maximum 2.5-fold improvement in odds of achieving mRS 0-1, with a decline to no treatment effect at 5 hours 28 minutes post-onset. The observed beneficial effect is very similar to Emberson's meta-analysis⁸ of a maximum 2.0-fold improvement in odds of achieving mRS 0-1, with a decline to no treatment effect at 6 hours 18 minutes post-onset.

3.4 Paper 4: Are the patients who would benefit from thrombolysis the same ones as those receiving it? A machine learning study of the UK stroke registry.⁴

Study type and population

Explainable machine learning model to investigate thrombolysis decision making (at stroke team level) and clinical benefit of thrombolysis. The model was based on 6 years of emergency ischaemic stroke admissions that arrived at an acute stroke team in England and Wales by ambulance after their stroke onset, had their scan within 255 minutes of stroke onset, and were not receiving anticoagulants for atrial fibrillation (78,396 patients). Includes 111 acute stroke hospitals (each with at least 250 stroke admissions and at least 10 thrombolysis procedures in the study period).

Key findings

- 44% of the study population received thrombolysis. 60% of the study population were predicted to benefit from thrombolysis (improved probability-weighted mRS and reduced probability of mRS 5-6).
- 73% of those treated were predicted to have a better outcome with thrombolysis, and 49% of those not treated were predicted to have a better outcome with thrombolysis.
- Patients with mismatched treatment decisions (actual thrombolysis use vs. predicted to benefit) cannot be identified from any one isolated feature value (such as stroke severity).
- Individual hospitals vary in balancing maximising benefit from thrombolysis vs. avoiding any possible harm.

3.5 Paper 5: Identifying levers for improving thrombolysis use and outcomes – combining clinical pathway simulation and machine learning applied to the UK stroke registry.⁵

Study type and population

Clinical pathway simulation, mathematical outcome modelling, and machine learning were used to investigate thrombolysis decision making and outcomes after stroke. The model was based on 5 years of all emergency stroke arrivals, by ambulance, to hospitals in England and Wales (302,715 patients).

Key findings

- Combining pathway improvements (improving arrival-to-thrombolysis times to 30 mins, reducing ambulance call-to-hospital-arrival times by 15 minutes, having all teams attain the current upper-quartile performance in determining stroke onset time, and applying decision making similar to high thrombolysing units) would be expected to increase thrombolysis use in patients arriving by ambulance from 13% to 20% and double the clinical benefit (additional patients discharged with mRS 0-1) from thrombolysis.
- The largest single factor in improving both thrombolysis use and outcomes is differences in clinical decision-making. Stroke teams vary in clinical decision-making especially in subgroups of patients with features that make them non-ideal candidates for thrombolysis: mild stroke, pre-existing disability, and imprecisely known stroke onset times.
- High thrombolysing units are predicted to be generating more net benefit (including better avoidance of mortality and severe disability) than low thrombolysing units.
- Improving speed and consistency of the emergency stroke pathway would improve thrombolysis use a little, but speed improvements (both pre-hospital and in-hospital) would have a larger effect on patient benefit.
- A health economics model, using the output from the outcome prediction model, estimated that thrombolysis produces an additional 0.26 QALY for each person treated.

4 Paper 1 highlights: Stroke physicians' and staff perspectives on machine learning to optimise thrombolysis decision making in stroke: a qualitative study.¹

4.1 Objective

What should a machine-learning model based on SSNAP data look like, do, and deliver if it is to optimise improvement, and reduce unwarranted variation, in thrombolysis?

1. To generate empirically and theoretically informed knowledge about how thrombolysis is currently delivered, centred on physicians' views, understandings, and practices.
2. To learn more about how stroke physicians' and staff think and feel about or use SSNAP, and about the use of machine learning in improving clinical practice.

4.2 Methods overview

We used focussed observations, semi-structured interviews and documentary analysis, to examine perceptions of thrombolysis, SSNAP, and machine learning. The NASSS (non-adoption, abandonment, scale-up, spread, sustainability) framework²¹ was used as a sensitising device to help us understand socio-technical factors likely to affect adoption and scale-up of SAMueL-2 technology.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 participants from the three observation sites and five key informants (senior clinicians/managers involved in stroke initiatives) based at other sites. The number of participants by role was:

- *Consultant*: 11 stroke, 3 emergency department (ED), 1 care of the elderly
- *Associate specialist doctor (ED)*: 1 ED
- *Registrar*: 1 stroke, 1 ED
- *Stroke assessor & nurse*: 2
- *Stroke nurse*: 1
- *Advanced clinical practitioner (stroke)*: 1
- *Stroke unit administrator*: 1
- *Information technology (IT) co-ordinator (stroke)*: 1
- *Integrated Stroke Delivery Network (ISDN) manager*: 1

Observation of healthcare professionals and work practices involved in the acute stroke pathway in three NHS Trusts (acute hospitals) in England (hereafter referred to as Sites A, B and C) was conducted. We used SSNAP data to purposefully select hospitals with low rates of thrombolysis and ensured they had differing stroke pathways and were geographically dispersed. 184 hours of focussed observation across the three sites comprising a variety of day/evening/night and weekend shifts was conducted, observing stroke care as well as clinical governance and multi-disciplinary team stroke review and SSNAP review meetings. Additionally, observation of online meetings of ISDNs and other organisations with strategic overview of stroke services in the NHS took place, with a focus on thrombolysis.

A third source of data was documents: we collected Trust-level documents (such as thrombolysis protocols and quality improvement, QI, initiative documentation); policy and strategy documents at ISDN level; computer modellers' presentations to stakeholders (clinicians, senior managers, policymakers); modelling team summaries of feedback from stakeholders.

4.3 Key results

We present findings in relation to six NASSS domains: (1) the condition, (2) the technology, (3) the value proposition, (4) the intended adopters, (5) the healthcare organisation, and (6) the wider system.

4.3.1 Domain 1: The condition

Physicians emphasised the heterogeneous and complex nature of the presentation of patients with stroke. They frequently used the concept ‘barn door’ to refer to a situation when a patient was perceived to be presenting with ‘classic’ symptoms of ischaemic stroke and where guidelines for treatment with thrombolysis could easily be followed and decision-making was straight-forward. However, physicians suggested most patients were not ‘barn-door’ presentations (also known as *clinical grey areas*), making decisions regarding thrombolysis more challenging.

Clinicians stressed the complexity of decision-making with respect to thrombolysis, particularly in clinical grey areas, and the perceived level of risk involved in the procedure. They discussed weighing up the risks/benefits in each case and challenges of obtaining informed consent for thrombolysis.

Clinicians characterised themselves and colleagues as pro or anti-thrombolysis, or keen or reluctant thrombolysers, the latter typically because they had experience of negative patient outcomes following thrombolysis and/or were generally more risk averse. Some reservations were also expressed about targets to improve thrombolysis rates.

4.3.2 Domain 2: The technology

Participants from one of the sites emphasised the necessity of the SAMueL-2 technology incorporating data on the configuration of acute stroke services for it to be seen as having validity. Most participants expressed having trust and confidence in SSNAP data and some referred to its potential to improve stroke services, but not all understood or engaged with the programme and thus were unsure how machine learning from SSNAP data could improve thrombolysis decision-making. Others were more enthusiastic about the potential for machine learning to extend the utility of SSNAP as a learning system for quality improvement. The addition of machine learning to the SSNAP portal was mooted as improving its sensitivity and potential for quality improvement vis-à-vis thrombolysis.

Some clinicians discussed their current use of AI based systems such as Brainomix or RapidAI and showed interest in SAMueL-2 becoming interoperable with these systems. Others expressed scepticism.

4.3.3 Domain 3: The value proposition

Reporting in this NASSS domain focusses on perceived demand-side value (while perceived supply-side value is reported as part of Domain 6 ‘The Wider System’). SAMueL-2 can be characterised as being at the value promise *developmental* stage; our data reflects the perceived or anticipated value of the technology which is relatively speculative.

SAMueL-2 was seen by some as providing the potential to address variation in clinical practice between clinicians and across trusts. Many participants perceived value in the potential for machine learning to help them in clinical grey areas when decision-making was most difficult, but there was uncertainty and ambivalence regarding whether this would/could happen during the acute stroke pathway. They hoped the SAMueL-2 technology would provide more specific and objective assessments of risk/benefit of the procedure and inform consent discussions. Some perceived it to be inevitable that AI/machine learning would eventually be used in real-time at the point of care. Some clinicians saw the value of the web app benchmarking feature to change culture or local thrombolysis guidelines. However, it was emphasised that this benchmarking should include data on patient complications and outcomes for it to be seen as valid and useful.

Participants discussed the perceived utility of the SAMueL-2 technology as a ‘learning tool’ to review clinical cases and provide training or quality assurance, for example at governance meetings. It was perceived as being useful as a decision-aid for trainees, non-stroke specialists and at district general hospitals.

4.3.4 Domain 4: The intended adopters

Some ED physicians were less confident about the evidence base for thrombolysis. They expressed a lack of faith in the clinical trials and reluctance to thrombolysed due to perceived risks of the procedure. One said they preferred thrombectomy to thrombolysis because they perceived that thrombectomy had more robust evidence to support it and fewer risks associated with it.

Some interviewees asserted that the web app benchmarking feature was not suitable or useful for experienced consultants like themselves, emphasising trust in their own clinical acumen. Others worried about how benchmarking and comparison

might be used and were anxious about how it might affect them. Concern was also expressed that AI might be given primacy over clinical decision-making and that this could adversely affect patient outcome.

4.3.5 Domain 5: The healthcare organisation

Participants discussed recent successful quality improvement initiatives regarding stroke, for example, improvement in door-to-needle times. For example, site A had initiated a stroke quality improvement week, and Site B had undertaken a reconfiguration of the acute stroke pathway which involved new stroke nurse assessor roles and stroke healthcare assistants. Each team member had been designated specific tasks facilitating speed of the acute pathway. Most participants at site B felt confident in the acute stroke processes and that there was readiness for organisational change. One participant suggested that there was potential for experienced non-consultant level staff to thrombolysise without a consultant being present to speed up the process.

However, participants also described organisational-level barriers they perceived to be impeding thrombolysis provision, such as:

- inexperienced clinical leadership
- workforce shortages and lack of specialist and experienced stroke nurses
- bureaucracy
- limited availability of imaging
- a culture that doesn't support use of thrombolysis
- funding constraints
- lack of access to computers
- overcrowding

Some people were enthusiastic that SAMueL-2 technology could be instrumental in overcoming these institutional barriers.

4.3.6 Domain 6: The wider system

Our analysis indicated that the wider professional and political context was important for adoption and scale-up of SAMueL-2. Stakeholders and participants from ISDNs were, with some expressed reservations about usability of the SSNAP interface, enthusiastic about SAMueL-2 being added to the portal and about facilitating its roll out to and uptake by sites for quality improvement.

The development of machine learning in conjunction with SSNAP was referred to by one national level policymaker as offering “the prospect of contributing significantly to reductions in stroke-related disability” [stakeholder communication] and was seen as having relevance to the NHS Long Term Plan. This appears to constitute a clear supply-side value proposition. The TASC initiative provided a ‘policy push’ for SAMueL-2 technology implementation, albeit initially on a limited scale.

4.4 Conclusions

In this study we drew on the NASSS framework to help understand the socio-technical factors likely to affect the adoption and scale-up of SAMueL-2 technology. We identified three learning points which may facilitate further implementation of the technology. First, given reservations expressed by some of our participants and healthcare professionals elsewhere about the underpinning SSNAP data it seems important to ensure that intended adopters are reassured about the integrity of modelling based on this data. Second, evidence from this research and elsewhere indicates that the ED physicians’ may have less confidence in the evidence base for, and safety of thrombolysis. It is therefore likely that more work will need to be done with the ED physician community to build trust in the SAMueL-2 technology: recruiting ED physicians as brokers/clinical champions may help to address this. Third, perceived lack of funding/resource and stroke workforce shortages may impede quality improvement and adoption of new technologies such as SAMueL-2. It will therefore be vital to address these concerns to ensure sustained use and adoption.

5 Paper 2 highlights: What would other emergency stroke teams do? Using explainable machine learning to understand variation in thrombolysis practice.²

5.1 Objective

To understand, using explainable machine learning, between-hospital variation in thrombolysis use among emergency stroke admissions in England and Wales.

5.2 Methods overview

Data were retrieved for 246,676 emergency stroke admissions to acute stroke teams in England and Wales for the years 2016–2018, obtained from the Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP). Data fields were provided for the hyper-acute phase of the stroke pathway, up to and including our target feature: receive thrombolysis. Of these patients, 88,928 were used in this modelling study: arrived within 4 hours of known stroke onset, had onset out of hospital, had an arrival to scan time recorded, and attended a hospital with at least 300 emergency stroke admissions and at least 10 thrombolysis procedures. A 4 hours onset-to-arrival cut-off was used to allow for 30 minutes for scan and thrombolysis to be within the allowed 4.5 onset-to-thrombolysis time. The data included 132 acute stroke hospitals. We trained a machine learning model (XGBoost²²) to learn which patients would receive thrombolysis at each stroke team. Shapley (SHAP) values were calculated for each prediction, providing estimates of how patient features, and hospital identity, influence the odds of receiving thrombolysis²³.

Code, and full results, for the machine learning work may be found at https://samuel-book.github.io/samuel_s_hap_paper_1

5.3 Key results

5.4 Feature selection

The best model with 1, 2, 5, 10, 25 & all 83 original features had ROC AUCs of 0.716, 0.792, 0.893, 0.919, 0.923 & 0.922. We selected 10 features for all subsequent work, which were:

- *Arrival-to-scan time*: Time from arrival at hospital to scan (minutes)
- *Infarction*: Stroke type (infarction/haemorrhage)
- *Stroke severity*: National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) score on arrival
- *Precise onset time*: Onset time (*precise*, or *best estimate*)
- *Prior disability level*: Estimated mRS score prior to stroke
- *Stroke team*: Stroke team attended (hospital identifier)
- *Use of atrial fibrillation (AF) anticoagulants*: Use of prior anticoagulants for atrial fibrillation.
- *Onset-to-arrival time*: Time from onset of stroke to arrival at hospital (minutes)
- *Onset during sleep*: Did stroke occur in sleep? (1 = Yes, 0 = No)
- *Age*: Age (as midpoint of 5 year age bands)

Correlations between the 10 features were measured using coefficients of determination (r-squared). All r-squared were less than 0.05 except (a) age and prior disability level (r-squared 0.146), and (b) onset during sleep and precise onset time (r-squared 0.078).

5.4.1 Model accuracy

Model accuracy was measured using stratified 5-fold cross validation. Overall accuracy was 85.0% (83.9% sensitivity and specificity could be achieved simultaneously). Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under Curve (ROC-AUC)

Figure 2: A waterfall plot for an example patient with model prediction and SHAP values expressed either as log odds (left) or probabilities (right). Predictions start with a base value (common to all predictions) of -0.058 log odds or 49.6% probability of receiving thrombolysis. The individual patient values then contribute to a final prediction of 2.505 log odds or 92.4% probability of receiving thrombolysis. The most influential features, all increasing the odds of receiving thrombolysis were no prior disability, a severe stroke (NIHSS 14), and 10 minutes onset-to-arrival time.

was 0.918 . The model predicted hospital thrombolysis use at each hospital with very good accuracy (r -squared = 0.977 , with a mean absolute error of 1.1 percentage points).

5.4.2 Individual patient prediction

SHAP values are calculated as log-odds as these are additive; the final model prediction, as log odds, is the sum of the individual feature SHAP values and the base SHAP value which is common to all predictions. For illustrative purposes, probabilities may also be used. Figure 2 shows SHAP values for an individual patient prediction. illustrated as a *waterfall* plot, shown as either log odds or probabilities.

5.4.3 Global patterns of patient factors affecting use of thrombolysis

Global patterns of how feature values affect the odds of receiving thrombolysis are constructed by combining all individual patient prediction SHAP values for each feature.

Figure 3 shows the relationship between patient characteristics and the log odds of receiving thrombolysis. Key observations are (with SHAP influence converted from log-odds to odds):

- *Stroke type*: The SHAP values for stroke type show that the model effectively eliminated any probability of receiving thrombolysis for non-*ischaemic* (*haemorrhagic*) stroke.
- *Arrival-to-scan time*: The odds of receiving thrombolysis reduced by about 9-fold over the first 120 minutes of arrival-to-scan time.
- *Stroke severity (NIHSS)*: The odds of receiving thrombolysis were lowest at NIHSS 0, increased and peaked at NIHSS 15-25, and then fell again with higher stroke severity (NIHSS above 25). The difference between minimum odds (at NIHSS 0) and maximum odds (at 15-25) of receiving thrombolysis was 25 to 30-fold.
- *Stroke onset time type (precise vs. estimated)*: The odds of receiving thrombolysis were about 3-fold greater for precise onset time than estimated onset time.
- *Disability level (mRS) before stroke*: The odds of receiving thrombolysis fell about 6-fold between mRS 0 and 5.
- *Use of AF anticoagulants*: The odds of receiving thrombolysis were about 5-fold greater for no use.
- *Onset-to-arrival time*: The odds of receiving thrombolysis were similar below 120 minutes, then fell about 3-fold between 120 and 240 minutes.
- *Age*: The odds of receiving thrombolysis were similar below 80 years old, then fell about 2-fold between 80 and 110 years old.

- *Onset during sleep*: The odds of receiving thrombolysis were about 4-fold lower for onset during sleep.

5.4.4 How hospital attended affects the odds of receiving thrombolysis

Figure 4 shows the distribution of SHAP values for hospital attended. The hospital SHAP value isolates the affect that attending any given hospital has on the odds of receiving thrombolysis. There was a 13-fold difference in odds of receiving thrombolysis between hospitals.

Overall we found 36% of the variance in observed between-hospital thrombolysis use can be explained by the patient population characteristics (age, stroke severity, prior disability, onset-to-arrival time, stroke type, type of onset time, anticoagulants, and onset during sleep), 74% can be explained by hospital identity and processes (arrival-to-scan time, and hospital attended), and that 95% can be explained by the combined information from both the patient population and hospital identity and processes.

We compared expected thrombolysis use in subgroups of patients. This is not included in this synopsis, as it is more clearly demonstrated in the *prototype patients* analysis in section 8. In summary we found all stroke teams were very likely to give thrombolysis to *ideal candidates* for thrombolysis, but they varied in their likelihood to give thrombolysis to patients with non-ideal characteristics such as mild stroke, imprecisely known onset time, or patients with pre-stroke disability.

5.5 Conclusions

Using explainable machine learning on a large national stroke registry dataset, we have identified how patient features and hospital attended influence decisions to treat with thrombolysis. We showed that the majority of the between-hospital variation in thrombolysis use in England and Wales, for patients arriving with time to thrombolysed, is explained by differences between in-hospital processes and differences in attitudes to eligibility for thrombolysis.

Figure 3: Box plots showing the relationship between SHAP values and feature values. Box plots show inter-quartile range (box), median (mid-line in box), and range (whiskers). The plots are ordered in ranked feature importance (using the mean absolute SHAP value across all instances).

Figure 4: Histogram showing the frequency of SHAP values for the hospital attended.

6 Paper 3 highlights: Thrombolysis: Are the results from the clinical trial meta-analysis seen in real life outcomes? A machine learning study of the UK stroke registry.³

6.1 Objective

To investigate, using explainable machine learning, the benefit of thrombolysis, and to compare the relationship between time-to-treatment and effectiveness with clinical trial results.

6.2 Methods overview

Data for a total of 168,347 ischaemic stroke patients who attended one of 118 emergency stroke hospitals in England and Wales from 2016 to 2021 were extracted from the Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP). We used explainable machine learning (XGBoost²² with SHAP²³) to examine the effect of patient characteristics, hospital attended, and use/time of thrombolysis on the odds of achieving a good outcome (being at or below any given modified Rankin Scale threshold). A linear regression model was fitted to the estimated effect of onset-to-treatment time on thrombolysis to permit comparison with clinical trial meta-analyses.

Code, and full results, for the machine learning work may be found at https://github.com/samuel-book/thrombolysis_clinical_trials_ml_paper

6.3 Key results

6.3.1 Feature selection

Using the results from Pearn *et al.*⁴, we selected seven features as inputs for the model to predict a patient's likelihood of a good outcome at discharge:

1. Prior disability level: Estimated mRS score prior to stroke
2. Stroke severity: National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) score on arrival
3. Stroke team: Stroke team attended (hospital identifier)
4. Age: Age (as midpoint of 5 year age bands)
5. Onset to thrombolysis time: Time from onset to receiving thrombolysis (minutes). This was set to 9999 if the patient did not receive thrombolysis.
6. Atrial fibrillation diagnosis: Patient had a diagnosis of atrial fibrillation, either on arrival or diagnosed during admission
7. Precise onset time known: Onset time recorded was recorded as being precise time, as opposed to a best estimate (*precise* or *best estimate*)

Code and full results for feature selection may be found at https://github.com/samuel-book/feature_selection_thrombolysis_outcome_ml_paper

6.3.2 Model accuracy

With 7 input features, overall accuracy ranged from 77.6% to 89.7% across the six models (standard deviation across the 5 k-folds ranged from 0.001 to 0.002). This represented between 95-98% of the accuracy that is obtained with all the features as inputs. Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under Curve (ROC-AUC) ranged from 0.852 to 0.893 across the six models (standard deviation across the 5 k-folds ranged from 0.001 to 0.002).

6.3.3 Global SHAP patterns

SHAP values explain the contribution (as the change in log-odds) that each feature value has on the model's prediction of achieving a good outcome at discharge²³. SHAP values expressed as log-odds are additive (and so are preferred to

probabilities, which are not additive, when examining the contribution of individual features to the final prediction). A SHAP model for each of the six machine learning models was created (one for each threshold of mRS to define a good outcome). To illustrate how to interpret the SHAP value in our case, the target feature with a value of 1 represents a good outcome (being at or below any given mRS threshold), and a value 0 represents a worse outcome (being above any given mRS threshold). A positive SHAP value represents that the corresponding feature value increases the likelihood for that patient having a good outcome, and a negative SHAP value represents that the corresponding feature value reduces the likelihood for that patient having a good outcome. SHAP values can be assessed *locally* at patient level, and *globally* at patient cohort level to understand general patterns of how discharge outcomes differ by each of the patient, pathway, and hospital characteristics.

For each patient in the test set we extracted SHAP values for each feature with its corresponding feature value. Figure 5a shows the relationship between feature values and the odds of a patient having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge (a positive SHAP value contributes to an increased likelihood, and a negative SHAP value contributes to a reduced likelihood). We see that low prior disability, lower stroke severity, younger age, receiving thrombolysis (and receiving it sooner after onset), and having no diagnosis of atrial fibrillation contributed to a patient more likely having a good outcome at discharge. Figure 5b focusses on the feature *onset to thrombolysis time*, and its effect at reaching any disability threshold. As time from onset to treatment increased, the beneficial effect of thrombolysis decayed. For thresholds up to, and including, mRS 3, the median effect of thrombolysis remained positive, compared to not receiving thrombolysis, up until the maximum time of 720 minutes. For thresholds of mRS 4 and upwards, the median effect of thrombolysis became negative at longer onset-to-treatment times. This was especially apparent in how thrombolysis changed the overall odds of survival (mRS 0-5) where the median effect of thrombolysis became negative from about 155 minutes. Later thrombolysis may therefore increase the proportion of patients attaining mRS 0-3, but at the cost of some reduction in overall survival. Earlier thrombolysis improved the odds of survival. Figure 5c shows the contribution from attending a specific hospital to predicting whether the patient had a good outcome at discharge, for each of the mRS threshold levels used to define a good outcome. As the threshold for having a good outcome becomes more inclusive, the range of the effect of the hospital attended had a reduced contribution on the prediction.

6.3.4 The direct contribution of thrombolysis use to the shift in probability of a good outcome

We used the first k-fold train/test set split (4:1 train:test data) to investigate likely outcome from thrombolysis. For each patient in the test set that received thrombolysis within 300 minutes from stroke onset ($n = 6,796$), we performed a counterfactual analysis, predicting outcome probabilities if the patient had not received thrombolysis. We calculated the effect of thrombolysis by taking the difference in SHAP values, between treated and the predicted outcome if untreated, for the contribution of thrombolysis to achieving a good outcome.

We modelled the decay in effect of thrombolysis by fitting a linear regression model to the benefit of thrombolysis (log odds shift in attaining a good outcome) with time from onset to treatment (excluding patients treated after 300 minutes). The model used the definition of mRS 0-1 as a good outcome to match the definition used in the meta-analysis of clinical trials⁸. The analysis was applied to three patient cohorts: (1) all treated ischaemic strokes ($n = 6,796$), (2) treated severe ischaemic strokes, NIHSS 11+ ($n = 2,856$), (3) treated mild-moderate ischaemic strokes, NIHSS 0-10 ($n = 3,940$).

Figure 6 shows a linear regression fitted to the shift in the contribution from receiving thrombolysis towards having a good outcome at discharge (mRS 0-1) with respect to the onset to thrombolysis time. We found, for all treated patients, that the effect of thrombolysis had declined to zero at 328 minutes, and the effect from thrombolysis was improving log odds of a good outcome by 0.90 if it were, theoretically, given at the time of stroke onset. We observed that the maximum theoretical effect of thrombolysis (if given at time of stroke onset) was greater for the severe stroke group (1.048 log odds) than the mild-moderate stroke group (0.771 log odds). However the effect of thrombolysis declined a little faster in the severe stroke group (reaching no effect at 314 minutes for severe stroke patients, compared to 351 minutes for mild-moderate stroke patients). Linear regression coefficients in all three patient groups were statistically significant (table 1).

Table 1: Fitting linear regression to the shift in the contribution from receiving thrombolysis towards having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge with respect to the onset to thrombolysis (OTT) time. Linear regression statistics for different patient cohorts. We used NIHSS 0-10 to define mild-moderate strokes, and NIHSS 11+ to define severe strokes.

Ischaemic stroke type	Variables	coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
All	Constant	0.9012	0.007	132.519	0.000	0.888	0.915
	OTT time (min)	-0.0027	4.04e-05	-68.058	0.000	-0.003	-0.003
Severe	Constant	1.0476	0.011	96.746	0.000	1.026	1.069
	OTT (mins)	-0.0033	6.67e-05	-50.042	0.000	-0.003	-0.003
Mild-moderate	Constant	0.7708	0.008	97.613	0.000	0.755	0.786
	OTT time (mins)	-0.0022	4.57e-05	-48.109	0.000	-0.002	-0.002

6.4 Conclusions

Using machine learning methods with SHAP in a very large prospective national stroke registry, thrombolysis was found to be associated with a statistically significant improvement in the odds of having a good outcome using any mRS threshold. Regression analysis predicted a maximum 2.5-fold improvement in odds of achieving mRS 0-1, with a decline to no treatment effect at 5 hours 28 minutes post-onset. The findings from this study were remarkably similar to the meta-analysis of clinical trials 8, which extrapolate back to a 0.69 log odds (equivalent to an odds ratio of 2.0) improvement of being mRS 0-1 at stroke onset, with no effect after 6 hours 18 minutes.

(a) The relationship between feature values and the prediction of whether a patient will have a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge. SHAP base value for this model is -1.529 .

(b) The relationship between onset to thrombolysis time and the prediction of whether a patient will have a good outcome at discharge, for each of the mRS scores used to define a good outcome.

(c) The contribution from attending a specific hospital to predicting whether the patient will have a good outcome at discharge, for each of the mRS scores used to define a good outcome

Figure 5: The relationship between feature values SHAP values in predicting whether a patient will have a good outcome. Violin plots show the distribution of SHAP values across the patient population for each feature value, with the mid-line showing the median SHAP value.

Figure 6: A linear regression fit to the contribution from receiving thrombolysis in having a good outcome (mRS 0-1) at discharge, with respect to the onset to thrombolysis time (for patients treated within 300 minutes). Top: all treated stroke patients ($n = 6,796$); Middle: treated severe stroke patients, NIHSS 11+ ($n = 2,856$); Bottom: treated mild-moderate stroke patients, NIHSS 0-10 ($n = 3,940$).

7 Paper 4 highlights: Are the patients who would benefit from thrombolysis the same ones as those receiving it? A machine learning study of the UK stroke registry.⁴

7.1 Objective

To investigate, using explainable machine learning, the overlap and differences between the groups of patients receiving thrombolysis, and the group of patients predicted to benefit from thrombolysis.

7.2 Methods overview

7.2.1 Outcome prediction

Data for a total of 78,396 ischaemic stroke patients who attended one of 111 emergency stroke hospitals in England and Wales and had brain imaging within 255 minutes of stroke onset, from 2016 to 2021, were extracted from the Sentinel Stroke National Audit Programme (SSNAP). We used explainable machine learning (XGBoost²² with SHAP²³) to examine the effect of patient characteristics, hospital attended, and use/time of thrombolysis on the patients' predicted outcome (modified Rankin Scale, mRS) at discharge. The data excludes patients on anticoagulants for atrial fibrillation (representing 12.9% of the population) as these patients may be at risk of adverse outcome that is not predicted by the machine learning model (as it is likely thrombolysis is only given to patients on anticoagulants when when it has been shown that blood clotting is normal).

The model predicts probability of each mRS category outcome. *Probability-weighted mRS* was used as a measure of the mid-point location of disability; it is the sum of each mRS outcome multiplied by the probability of that outcome occurring

We predicted the expected effect of thrombolysis for all patients, and compared who would benefit from thrombolysis with those who actually received thrombolysis. We used a conservative definition to determine whether a patient would likely have a better outcome with treatment from the two probability distributions, where both of these criteria must be met:

1. a reduction in probability-weighted mRS, **and**
2. a reduction in the likelihood of a very bad outcome (mRS 5-6, complete dependency or death).

7.2.2 Hospital trade-off between maximising benefit from thrombolysis and minimising risk of harm from thrombolysis

We trained a separate XGBoost *thrombolysis decision* model, to predict the likelihood of a patient receiving thrombolysis, using methods previously described². We used this to predict likely thrombolysis use for all patients at all stroke teams. This was used to compare likely decision-making and outcomes across if all stroke teams saw the same patients. To compare maximising benefit from thrombolysis and avoiding potential harm from thrombolysis we defined measures for *sensitivity* and *specificity* of treatment. *Sensitivity* was calculated as the proportion of patients who were predicted to benefit from thrombolysis (from the *thrombolysis outcome* model) who were predicted to receive thrombolysis at each team (from the *thrombolysis decision* model). *Specificity* was calculated as the proportion of patients who were predicted not to benefit from thrombolysis (from the *thrombolysis outcome* model) who were not predicted to receive thrombolysis at each team (from the *thrombolysis decision* model). A low *sensitivity* would indicate a higher likelihood of not treating people who would benefit from thrombolysis, and a low *specificity* would indicate a higher likelihood of treating people who would not benefit from thrombolysis.

Code, and full results, for the machine learning work may be found at https://github.com/samuel-book/thrombolysis_outcome_ml_paper.

7.3 Key results

7.3.1 Feature selection

We selected seven features as inputs for the model to predict a patient’s likelihood of a good outcome at discharge:

1. Prior disability level: Estimated mRS score prior to stroke
2. Stroke severity: National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) score on arrival
3. Stroke team: Stroke team attended (hospital identifier)
4. Age: Age (as midpoint of 5 year age bands)
5. Onset to thrombolysis time: Time from onset to receiving thrombolysis (minutes). This was set to 9999 if the patient did not receive thrombolysis.
6. Atrial fibrillation diagnosis: Patient had a diagnosis of atrial fibrillation, either on arrival or diagnosed during admission (1 = Yes, 0 = No)
7. Precise onset time known: Onset time recorded was recorded as being precise time, as opposed to a best estimate (1 = precise, 0 = best estimate)

Code and full results for feature selection may be found at https://github.com/samuel-book/feature_selection_thrombolysis_outcome_ml_paper

7.3.2 Model accuracy

Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under Curve (ROC-AUC) was 0.796 (0.001 standard deviation across the 5 k-folds). Classification accuracy across the seven mRS outcomes was 41.1% (0.002 standard deviation across the 5 k-folds). Accuracy to within one mRS category was 72.4% (0.002 standard deviation across the 5 k-folds).

7.4 Comparing actual use of thrombolysis and predicted benefit from thrombolysis

We used the first k-fold train/test set split (4:1 train:test data) to investigate likely outcome from thrombolysis. In the test set of 15,680 patients, 44% received thrombolysis. For each patient we predicted outcomes with and without thrombolysis. Figure 7 shows the expected shift in probability-weighted mRS at discharge, and the change in probability of being discharged with mRS 5-6, due to thrombolysis, separated by whether the patient actually received thrombolysis or not. Overall, 60% of patients were predicted to benefit from thrombolysis. Of those who did receive thrombolysis, 73% were predicted to have both a better average disability likelihood and a reduction in probability of being mRS 5-6. 9% were predicted to have both a worse average disability likelihood and an increase in probability of being mRS 5-6. 18% were predicted to have either, but not both, a better average disability likelihood or a reduction in probability of being mRS 5-6. Of those who did not receive thrombolysis, 49% were predicted to have both a better average disability likelihood and a reduction in probability of being mRS 5-6. 26% were predicted to have both a worse average disability likelihood and an increase in probability of being mRS 5-6. 25% were predicted to have either, but not both, a better average disability likelihood or a reduction in probability of being mRS 5-6.

7.5 Patient characteristics that contribute to a mismatch between actual thrombolysis use and predicted best outcome

We compared the distribution of feature values for two patient cohorts: i) patients that received thrombolysis but were predicted to not have a better outcome with thrombolysis, ii) patients that did not receive thrombolysis but were predicted to have a better outcome with thrombolysis. When examining individual feature values in this way we did not identify any features that could be used in isolation to identify those patients who would benefit from thrombolysis but did not receive thrombolysis (or vice-versa). Patients who received thrombolysis but would likely not benefit from it have a range of feature values for each patient feature, as do those patients who did not receive thrombolysis but would benefit from it.

(a) Patients who received thrombolysis (n = 6,916)

(b) Patients who did not receive thrombolysis (n = 8,764)

Figure 7: The predicted benefit or disbenefit of thrombolysis for each of the 15,680 patients in the first k-fold test set. Benefit is shown as both the expected improvement in probability-weighted disability (y-axis) and the improvement in likelihood of avoiding discharge with mRS 5-6. Both measures are expressed so that a positive value is better (a reduction in probability-weighted disability or a reduction in probability of discharge with mRS 5-6). (a) Patients who did actually receive thrombolysis (n = 6,916), (b) Patients who did not actually receive thrombolysis (n = 8,764).

Figure 8: *Sensitivity* (proportion of patients who were predicted to benefit from thrombolysis who were predicted to receive thrombolysis) and *specificity* (proportion of patients who were predicted *not* to benefit from thrombolysis who were predicted *not* to receive thrombolysis) for each stroke team. The dotted line shows the hospitals on the Pareto front where there are no hospitals that have a better *sensitivity* without a worse *specificity*, or vice-versa.

7.6 Hospital trade-off between maximising benefit from thrombolysis and minimising risk of harm from thrombolysis

The XGBoost *thrombolysis decision* model had an accuracy of 78.7% and ROC-AUC of 0.86. Figure 8 shows the trade-off between the individual hospitals *sensitivity* and *specificity* towards giving treatment. We found that those hospitals attaining a higher predicted *sensitivity* of treatment (not missing patients who would benefit from treatment) also tended to have a lower *specificity* (giving thrombolysis to patients who would likely not benefit from it).

7.7 Conclusions

Using machine learning with SHAP in a very large national stroke registry dataset, we found general agreement between actual thrombolysis use and best predicted outcomes, though we found decisions based on the outcome model would support higher use of thrombolysis than is actually the case. Of those who did not receive thrombolysis, the outcome model predicted that nearly half of them would have likely benefited from thrombolysis. Of those that did receive thrombolysis we found about one in four may be being given thrombolysis without there being predicted benefit. There was an apparent trade-off in decision-making between hospitals. Those hospitals who gave thrombolysis to more patients who would benefit from it (higher *sensitivity*) were also more likely to give thrombolysis to more patients who would not benefit from it (lower *specificity*). This represents a trade-off between ‘*Miss no benefit*’ and ‘*Do no harm*’. Maximising benefit while minimising harm is likely to require more sophisticated guidance on use of thrombolysis, such as that indicated by our model.

8 Paper 5 highlights: Identifying levers for improving thrombolysis use and outcomes – combining clinical pathway simulation and machine learning applied to the UK stroke registry.⁵

8.1 Objective

By combining clinical pathway simulation and machine learning of thrombolysis decision-making and outcomes, we sought to better understand the source of variation in thrombolysis use and the effect on outcomes. We also sought to investigate the cost-effectiveness of thrombolysis in stroke teams with lower or higher thrombolysis use.

8.2 Methods overview

8.2.1 Models

This work combined four models:

1. *Thrombolysis decision model*: An XGBoost machine learning model²² was used to learn which patients would receive thrombolysis at each stroke team. Stroke team SHAP values were used to identify 25 *benchmark teams* most likely to use thrombolysis. For each patient a *benchmark decision* was predicted, which was the majority vote of the expected decision for that patient at the 25 *benchmark teams*. This is based on the model as described in section 5.
2. *Outcome model*: A XGBoost machine learning model was used to predict outcome (mRS probability distribution) for each patient. This is based on the model as described in section 7.
3. *Patient pathway flow*: Monte-Carlo simulation was used to model the flow of patients through the emergency stroke pathway at each hospital, taking into account both average speeds and variation. When examining the effect of improving patient flow, clinical outcome is predicted as the number of *excellent outcomes* (mRS 0-1) per 1,000 admissions using a previously described mathematical model²⁴.
4. *Lifetime economic model*: A model predicting life expectancy, quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), and NHS care costs after stroke, based on age, sex, and disability at discharge²⁵.

8.2.2 Prototype patients

To help compare decision-making and outcomes across stroke teams we exemplified differences using *prototype patients*. These prototype patients captured a range of features known to affect decisions to treat, and to affect outcomes, and included an *ideal* candidate for thrombolysis. The prototype patients used were:

1. *Ideal*: Onset-to-arrival = 90 minutes; arrival-to-scan = 15 minutes; onset-to-thrombolysis = 120 minutes; stroke severity (NIHSS) = 15; pre-stroke disability (mRS) = 0; age = 72.5; precisely known onset; onset not during sleep; stroke type = infarction; patient has no atrial fibrillation and is not receiving anticoagulants for atrial fibrillation.
2. *Late arrival*: As *ideal* but onset-to-arrival = 225 minutes and onset-to-thrombolysis (when given) = 255 minutes.
3. *Mild*: As *ideal* but stroke severity = 3.
4. *Prior disability*: As *ideal* but pre-stroke disability = 3
5. *Imprecise*: As *ideal* but stroke onset time estimated.
6. *Age*: As *ideal* but age = 87.5.
7. Combinations of the above.

8.2.3 Pathway changes

The combined model may be used to examine a range of possible changes to improve use of thrombolysis:

1. *Base*: Uses the hospitals' recorded pathway statistics.

2. *Speed*: Sets 95% of patients having a scan within 4 hours of arrival (other assumed to be late scan, due to atypical stroke symptoms), and all patients have 15 minutes arrival-to-scan time and 15 minutes scan-to-needle time.
3. *Ambo*: Subtracts 15 minutes from the current ambulance-call to arrival-at-hospital times.
4. *Onset-known*: Sets the proportion of patients with a known stroke onset time to the national upper quartile (79.6%) if currently less than the national upper quartile.
5. *Benchmark*: The benchmark thrombolysis rate takes the likelihood to give thrombolysis for patients scanned within 4 hours of onset from the majority vote of the 25 benchmark hospitals (see above).
6. Combinations of the above.

Code, with demonstration, is available at https://github.com/samuel-book/samuel_2_demo.

8.3 Key results

8.4 Model accuracy

Using an 4:1 train:test split, the thrombolysis decision model had an accuracy of 85%, a balanced accuracy (mean of sensitivity and specificity) of 82% (accuracy and balanced accuracy using a 50% probability cut-off to classify a patient as a binary ‘likely to receive thrombolysis’ or not), and a receiver operating characteristic area under curve of 0.92. The stroke outcome model had a receiver operating characteristic area under curve of 0.80.

8.5 Benchmark stroke teams and benchmark decisions

Benchmark decisions are those that would likely be taken by the majority 25 *benchmark* stroke teams most likely to use thrombolysis (if all stroke teams saw the same patients). If all decisions-to-treat were made according to benchmark decisions, the average thrombolysis rate across stroke teams would increase from 36% to 45% (in the modelled patient population). Thrombolysis use in the 25 stroke teams least likely to use thrombolysis would increase from 29% to 46%.

Figure 9 compares observed and predicted thrombolysis use (based on historic performance, and applying *benchmark decisions*). Predicted and observed thrombolysis use correlate very closely (r-squared 0.94). Predicted rates were, on average, slightly higher (1.7%) than observed rates.

8.5.1 Prototype patients

Prototype patients revealed variation in likely decisions between stroke teams (figure 10). While almost all stroke teams would give thrombolysis to the *ideal* candidate for thrombolysis, the predicted use of thrombolysis varied more as one characteristic was changed from the *ideal* candidate. In particular there was a very wide range in likelihood of a patient with a mild stroke (NIHSS 3) receiving thrombolysis. Mild stroke (NIHSS 0-4) represents a large proportion of admissions (54% of all emergency stroke admissions, and 38% of ischaemic stroke patients arriving by ambulance within 4 hours of known stroke onset). Combinations of *non-ideal* patient characteristics reduced predicted use of thrombolysis further (again with significant variation between stroke teams), especially when the non-ideal characteristic was a mild stroke.

Table 2 shows predicted outcomes across all prototype patients. All these patients would likely benefit from thrombolysis, but the benefit in mild stroke was smaller.

Figure 9: Comparison of observed and predicted thrombolysis use across stroke teams. Blue circles show predictions based on historic hospital performance. Red circles show the expected thrombolysis use if *benchmark decisions* were made. The black dotted line shows least-squares regression analysis between observed and predicted (using historic performance) thrombolysis use.

Table 2: Predicted outcomes for patient prototypes. *Ideal*: onset-to-arrival = 90 minutes; arrival-to-scan = 15 minutes; onset-to-thrombolysis = 120 minutes; stroke severity (NIHSS) = 15; pre-stroke disability (mRS) = 0; age = 72.5; precisely known onset; onset not during sleep; stroke type = infarction; patient has no atrial fibrillation and is not receiving anticoagulants for atrial fibrillation. *Late arrival*: as *Ideal* but onset-to-arrival = 225 minutes and onset-to-thrombolysis = 255 minutes; *Mild*: as *Ideal* but stroke severity = 3; *Prior disability*: as *Ideal* but pre-stroke disability = 3; *Imprecise*: as *ideal* but stroke onset time estimated. *Age*: as *Ideal* but age = 87.5. Results also includes patients prototypes with combinations of these non-ideal characteristics. Results show probability-weighted disability at discharge, and the proportion of patients predicted to have a very poor outcome (mRS 5-6).

Patient prototype	Untreated probability-weighted mRS	Treated probability-weighted mRS	Improvement	Untreated proportion mRS 5-6	Treated proportion mRS 5-6	Improvement
Ideal	3.39	2.37	1.02	0.32	0.13	0.19
Late	3.39	2.73	0.66	0.32	0.18	0.14
Mild	1.15	0.91	0.23	0.01	0.01	0.00
Prior disability	4.22	3.61	0.61	0.41	0.23	0.19
Imprecise	3.49	2.39	1.10	0.33	0.13	0.20
Age	4.22	3.51	0.71	0.50	0.35	0.16
Mild + Prior disability	2.92	2.60	0.32	0.04	0.04	0.00
Mild + Imprecise	1.28	1.01	0.26	0.02	0.01	0.00
Mild + Age	1.84	1.63	0.22	0.04	0.03	0.01
Mild + Late	1.15	0.77	0.39	0.01	0.00	0.00
Imprecise + Prior disability	4.33	3.67	0.66	0.44	0.24	0.20
Imprecise + Age	4.31	3.57	0.74	0.53	0.36	0.17
Imprecise + Late	3.49	2.75	0.74	0.33	0.17	0.17
Prior disability + Age	4.62	4.35	0.27	0.53	0.44	0.08
Prior disability + Late	4.22	3.70	0.52	0.41	0.27	0.14
Mild + Prior disability + Imprecise	3.01	2.65	0.36	0.06	0.06	0.00

Figure 10: Violin plots showing the variation in predicted thrombolysis rates for 17 patient prototypes across stroke teams. *Ideal*: onset-to-arrival = 90 minutes; arrival-to-scan = 15 minutes; onset-to-thrombolysis = 120 minutes; stroke severity (NIHSS) = 15; pre-stroke disability (mRS) = 0; age = 72.5; precisely known onset; onset not during sleep; stroke type = infarction; patient has no atrial fibrillation and is not receiving anticoagulants for atrial fibrillation; *Late arrival*: as *ideal* but onset-to-arrival = 225 minutes and onset-to-thrombolysis = 255 minutes; *Mild*: As *ideal* but stroke severity = 3; *Prior disability*: as *ideal* but pre-stroke disability = 3; *Imprecise*: as *ideal* but stroke onset time estimated; *Age*: as *ideal* but age = 87.5.

Figure 11: Expected effect of alternative process improvement initiatives across the study population. The chart shows the effect on thrombolysis use (left) and on number of additional excellent outcomes (mRS 0-1) per 1,000 admissions due to use of thrombolysis (right). *Base*: Uses the hospitals' recorded pathway statistics. *Onset*: Sets the proportion of patients with a known stroke onset time to the national upper quartile if currently less than the national upper quartile. *Speed*: Sets 95% of patients having a scan within 4 hours of arrival, and all patients have 15 minutes arrival-to-scan time and 15 minutes scan-to-needle time. *Ambo*: Subtracts 15 minutes from the current ambulance call to arrival-at-hospital times. *Benchmark*: The benchmark thrombolysis rate takes the likelihood to give thrombolysis for patients scanned within 4 hours of onset from the majority vote of the 25 benchmark hospitals.

8.5.2 Pathway improvement

Across the study population, by combining pathway improvements, thrombolysis use in all those emergency stroke admissions arriving by ambulance shows the potential to be increased from 13% to 20% (figure 11). Using a model based on clinical trial data, benefit, as measured by number of number of people discharged with no, or minimal, disability (mRS 0 or 1) could be doubled from 10 to 20 additional excellent outcomes per 1,000 admissions. The single most influential change in improving thrombolysis use was applying *benchmark* decisions (figure 11, left panel). Improving speed would not greatly increase the number of people given thrombolysis, but would lead to more benefit from thrombolysis as all treated patients will gain benefit from earlier treatment (figure 11, left panel).

8.6 Lifetime economic model

Table 3 shows the modelled health economics of thrombolysis use, comparing actual use of thrombolysis with *benchmark* thrombolysis use. The effect of thrombolysis was estimated by predicting the outcomes with and without thrombolysis for the two groups (those that actually received thrombolysis, and those predicted to receive thrombolysis using *benchmark* decisions). Benchmark decisions maintain the benefit of using thrombolysis, but extend that benefit to more patients. This extended benefit was not at the cost of any predicted increase in the worst outcomes (mRS 5-6). The extended benefit led to more QALYs added across the population by treatment, and more predicted savings to NHS healthcare costs.

Table 3: Health economic analysis: Analysis for populations based on predicted benefit (or dis-benefit) of thrombolysis. The effect of thrombolysis was estimated by predicting the outcomes with and without thrombolysis for the two groups (those that actually received thrombolysis, and those predicted to receive thrombolysis using *benchmark* decisions). The analysis compares the populations currently treated, or the population that would be treated using *benchmark* decisions (the majority vote of the predicted choice of the the 25 stroke teams most likely to use thrombolysis). Results are shown for (a) the treated populations, and (b) adjusted for 1,000 emergency stroke admissions

(a) Analysis of the predicted effect of thrombolysis in two population subgroups: 1) those patients who actually received thrombolysis, or 2) those patients where the *benchmark decision* would be to use thrombolysis. For each populations the outcomes with and without thrombolysis were predicted.

Modelled population	Modelled treatment	Death	Survival (median years)	Care years (median)	QALYs	Discounted cost per patient	Proportion mRS 0-2	Proportion mRS 5-6
Actual use	Untreated	17.1%	7.60	0.28	5.020	£20,370	47.1%	23.9%
	Treated	14.2%	7.91	0.25	5.258	£19,806	53.9%	19.3%
	Difference	-2.9%	0.31	-0.03	0.238	-£565	6.8%	-4.7%
Benchmark	Untreated	17.4%	7.63	0.28	5.036	£20,388	46.5%	24.1%
	Treated	14.4%	7.93	0.25	5.269	£19,784	53.4%	19.4%
	Difference	-3.0%	0.30	-0.03	0.234	-£603	6.9%	-4.8%

(b) Analysis for 1,000 emergency stroke admissions (all stroke types)

Modelled population	Proportion treated	QALYs added	Healthcare costs saved	Thrombolysis cost (£450 per patient)	Cost per QALY added	Net cost of thrombolysis
Actual	11.0%	26.3	£62,294	£49,658	£1,890	-£12,637
Benchmark	13.6%	31.7	£81,914	£61,117	£1,927	-£20,797

8.7 Conclusions

There is significant inter-hospital variation in use of thrombolysis that is caused by hospital processes and differences in decision-making. Improving processes and adopting the decision making of higher-thrombolysing units would be expected to increase thrombolysis use and has the potential to double the population benefit from thrombolysis. Higher-thrombolysing sites are delivering greater cost-effectiveness from thrombolysis through reductions in long-term disability in a greater number of patients. Pathway analysis and machine learning should allow stroke teams to better understand, and improve, their own pathways.

9 Other project outputs

9.1 Predicting willingness to use thrombolysis from SSNAP organisational audit data

We performed a multiple regression model to investigate whether organisational audit results reported by SSNAP could be used to predict a teams. The SSNAP Organisational Audit collects biennial data on the structure and organization of acute hospital stroke services, including bed numbers, staffing and seniority levels (including at the ‘front door’), models of delivery of hyperacute services including reperfusion, and other structural data. We devised a model to investigate whether organisational audit data reported by SSNAP could be used to predict a team’s propensity to use thrombolysis, as measured by the SHAP value for the stroke team in the thrombolysis decision model. We were not able to identify any significant predictors of ‘willingness to thrombolysse’ from these data, indicating that there were no features of the organisation of hyperacute staffing or other provision, including unit size and admission numbers, that were predictive of a site’s propensity to use thrombolysis (see https://github.com/samuel-book/thrombolysis_organisational_factors/blob/main/data_prep/2c_statsmodels.ipynb). This finding runs counter to the often-cited notion that sites with higher rates of thrombolysis tend to be those that are larger and better staffed. Evidence is clear that organisation factors do affect thrombolysis use¹³; we simply did not find a strong link between willingness to use thrombolysis and the organisational audit output. This could be due to the SSNAP Organisational Audit recording numbers from a single day snap shot, and more frequent data collection may enable identification of significant predictors of ‘willingness to thrombolysse’.

9.2 Pilot thrombectomy model

As part of this study we performed a pilot experiment on the effect of thrombectomy (mechanical removal of the clot) on outcomes in moderate-severe stroke (NIHSS 6+). The same model method was used as the outcome modelling with thrombolysis, but time from onset to thrombectomy was also added as an input feature. Figure 12 shows the relationship between time from onset to thrombectomy. **These results have not been robustly investigated, and should be taken as indicative only**, but we saw a beneficial effect of thrombectomy. The beneficial effect of thrombectomy decayed over time; Early thrombectomy was able to significantly improve the odds of being discharged with mRS 0-2 (with this effect being in addition to the effect of thrombolysis). More work is required to confirm and better understand this effect, with the significantly larger number of patients who have received thrombectomy that is now in SSNAP.

Figure 12: The effect of time of onset to thrombectomy on the log of odds of being discharged with mRS 0-2 for patients with stroke severity of NIHSS 6+ (using the SHAP value for the effect of thrombectomy). Data shown is for patients that received thrombectomy within 10 hours of stroke onset. This effect is the effect of thrombectomy in addition to any effect of thrombolysis. **Results show pilot work and should be taken as indicative only.**

10 Discussion

10.1 Principal Findings

Principal findings are outlined in section 3.

10.2 Clinical Synopsis and Implications

This body of work has used the power of big data from the UK's comprehensive, prospective registry of hospitalised stroke, SSNAP, combined with new and sophisticated analytical techniques involving machine learning supported by qualitative research, to investigate one of the persisting controversies of acute stroke treatment over the last quarter-century – why, after such a long time, is there still such huge variation in the use of one of the most important disability-reducing treatments available for acute stroke? We are now long past the 25th anniversary of the publication of the landmark NINDS trial which was the first to demonstrate the benefits of reperfusion treatment with alteplase (thrombolysis) within 3 hours of stroke onset, and ten years on from the decisive meta-analysis of over 6,700 patients published in the *Lancet*⁸, yet the failure of the global clinical community to fully embrace the potential of treatment to reduce the most common cause of adult-onset disability worldwide remains at best an enigma, and at worst a damning failure of implementation.

One of the most common reasons cited for variation in clinical practice in thrombolysis is 'exceptionalism', or what we have termed the 'special hospital fallacy'. Clinicians often cite (usually based on hearsay rather than evidence) that the failure of their hospital to fully implement the findings of research and the recommendations of national expert bodies results from the unique nature of their local population, and the manner in which they differ from the highly selected participants in randomised controlled trials predominantly conducted in well resourced and large academic centres. Real-world research with a very large and comprehensive dataset enables these objections to be directly addressed, and our generalisable finding that the majority of between-hospital variation results not from differences in the local population but from differences in within-hospital factors, including propensity to thrombolys, is key to neutralising what for many is seen as the justification for inaction. We have, for example, shown a three-fold variation in thrombolysis use in patients presenting to hospital within four hours of onset according to whether the onset time is precisely known or witnessed compared to being a 'best estimate'. This clearly illustrates variation in the extent to which any given hospital team is prepared to thrombolys based on an estimated onset time – one aspect of a wider phenomenon best characterised as 'willingness to thrombolys'. This phenomenon is particularly evident when we examine the probability of thrombolysis being administered in any particular site to patients who are varying from the 'ideal' (often described, as it was in our qualitative study, as the 'barn door' case), often in relatively small ways. The willingness of different stroke teams to thrombolys these less-than-ideal cases is the principal source of variation in rates between hospital sites – particularly with reference to whether the patient was experiencing a milder stroke severity, or with more pre-stroke disability, or if the onset time was based on a best estimate rather than being precisely known or witnessed. It is therefore significant that our health economic work linked to pathway simulation and optimisation has shown that sites with a greater willingness to thrombolys are still delivering greater disability reductions and health economic benefits from their higher levels of thrombolysis use among less-than-ideal patients – using real-world data to refute the allegation that such sites are merely administering thrombolysis to people who do not stand to benefit or who do not conform to the more strictly applied eligibility of the original randomised trials. Indeed this work demonstrates that there is still significant residual population benefit to be gained from the greater use of thrombolysis in patients scanned within 4 hours and 15 minutes of onset – half of such patients who were not treated still stood to gain net benefit in reduced discharge disability, and a reasonable estimate of the proportion of this early-presenting cohort predicted to benefit from thrombolysis is 60% - when current thrombolysis rates among patients presenting within 4 hours of onset vary seven-fold between 7% and 49%. Increasing the speed and usage of thrombolysis in more patients offers the prospect of doubling the population benefit, as shown by the increase in the number of patients with an excellent outcome (mRS 0-1) from 10 to 20 additional excellent outcomes per 1,000 stroke admissions.

Another barrier to wider implementation is the perception that real-world use will fail to deliver the same benefits that were shown in the strictly regulated and controlled environment of a clinical trial. It is certainly the case that typical stroke patients in the UK and elsewhere are older and with more severe pre-stroke disability than those selected into

trials, many of which specified the exclusion of patients with a pre-stroke disability any higher than 1 on the modified Rankin Scale (mRS). Prospective registries play a crucial role in scrutinising the implementation of the primary trial evidence into real-world practice, and so it is an important conclusion from the advanced analysis contained in this work that thrombolysis is indeed delivering the anticipated benefits for large numbers of patients every year. We have observed a significant increase in the odds of achieving a good outcome (same-or-better mRS without an increased risk of severe disability or death) with thrombolysis at any threshold of mRS, despite the fact that patients in the SSNAP registry are less ideal in their clinical characteristics and are treated later than typical trial participants, when the absolute benefits would be expected to be reduced. There is significant reassurance available to clinicians and patients that the use of thrombolysis in usual clinical practice is indeed delivering the benefits expected from meta-analysis of the primary trials.

This translation into everyday clinical practice extends to cost-effectiveness. In extending the pathway simulation work with a health economic analysis, we have shown that current use of thrombolysis in the UK is expected to result in a 6.8% absolute increase in the proportion of patients with a discharge mRS of 0-2 at a net cost per QALY of £1,927. By current 'willingness to pay' thresholds (customarily £30,000 per QALY for any non-cancer treatment in the UK) this would indicate that the NHS is being extremely cost-effective in reducing lifelong stroke-related disability through the use of thrombolysis. Furthermore, because high-thrombolysing sites are delivering the treatment to more patients, this clinical and cost-effectiveness correspondingly increases, with a net annual saving of over £20,000 per 1,000 stroke admissions at a 'benchmark' site. If the willingness to thrombolyse seen in the top quartile of sites were reproduced across the NHS, this would save at least £2 million/year, principally through reductions in the costs of long term disability that are usually borne by families and by social care.

This cost-effectiveness also encompasses the tendency of benchmark hospitals to treat more patients with minor stroke (NIHSS 0-4). The effectiveness of thrombolysis in minor, or in non-disabling, stroke is the subject of current debate, with a recent Chinese study of thrombolysis with alteplase versus dual antiplatelet therapy in 'non-disabling' stroke²⁶ proving negative and a subsequent systematic review and meta-analysis indicating that thrombolysis does not improve disability outcomes or functional prognosis for patients with minor stroke²⁷. A similar effect is observed in our work, with a marginal increase in the proportion of those patients who present with NIHSS 0-4 that achieve a discharge mRS of 0-2 being counterbalanced by an equivalent marginal increase in the proportion with a discharge mRS of 5 or 6. We have, however, also demonstrated that there is no single feature, including the NIHSS total score, which reliably discriminates those patients who would or would not benefit from thrombolysis. This reflects the heterogeneity of stroke impairments and presentations, including the poorer relationship between NIHSS and outcomes in the posterior circulation, and underlines the observation that when considering whether a stroke is going to prove to be disabling or non-disabling in any individual patient, the NIHSS score cannot be the sole consideration²⁸. Given the overall net benefit from thrombolysis in high-thrombolysing sites demonstrated in our study, this does suggest that frontline clinicians are, in general, making appropriate decisions about treatment based on disability potential in patients presenting with NIHSS 0-4. There may well be more that can be done to improve discrimination in this group of patients using other parameters not measured in SSNAP (frailty, for example, or the inclusion of imaging data) that can refine decision-making for these patients. In the absence of a single feature that can readily discriminate between those who would and would not benefit at this milder end of the severity scale, the clinician must always primarily address the question 'For this patient, is this minor stroke still going to be disabling?'

These and other ambiguities and uncertainties in clinical practice and in the implementation of the research data are amply illustrated by the findings from the nested qualitative study. The findings from the machine learning work in this project will hopefully help to address the scepticism encountered in the qualitative work about the credibility of machine learning, and clinicians are understandably wary when it comes to computer modelling seeking to dissect and explain 'clinical judgement'. Hesitancy regarding the use of 'artificial intelligence' in other areas of clinical practice is widely described, and it is valuable learning from the qualitative work that there can be no inherent assumption that computerised methods, no matter how sophisticated, will be welcomed with open arms by busy clinicians who remain to be persuaded of the added value of these techniques²⁹. Scepticism about the benefits and risks of thrombolysis also extended into the historical reluctance among some emergency medicine physicians to accept the twenty-five year heritage of scientific research into the treatment both in Europe and the US, manifested by cautious statements of support from professional bodies such as the Royal College of Emergency Medicine³⁰. The extent to which this reluctance contributes to the overall variation in thrombolysis practice and treatment rates around the UK is debatable

– there are relatively few sites in the UK where emergency physicians are primarily responsible for the delivery of thrombolysis, although one of these was one of the three participating centres in the ethnographic research. Certainly the degree of observed variation in rates is far greater than could be accounted for purely by uncertainty among emergency physicians, and indicates much wider uncertainty among mainstream stroke physicians. Using large cohorts of patients from a national stroke registry, collected over several years, to provide objective analysis of clinical variation can be one method for highlighting the causes and consequences of such variation, but it is well recognised that clinical practice change is often frustratingly slow-moving and requires a multidimensional approach – there is no ‘silver bullet’. However, the bespoke nature of the estimates of additional treated patients and the corresponding gains in favourable outcomes provided by the pathway analysis work, and now freely available to all teams on the web app at <https://stroke-predictions.streamlit.app/>, does address at least two of the factors known to promote practice change identified by systematic review^{31;32} – the perceived relevance of the change in practice to the clinicians’ specific circumstances (through bespoke estimates based on their own local population), and the direct link to better patient outcomes, rather than intermediate or surrogate measures such as the thrombolysis rate as an end in itself. However, even with this improved quality improvement (QI) methodology, the qualitative research revealed that sites still felt they lacked the human and financial resources to fully exploit the QI potential of SAMueL-2, an observation that reiterates the importance of providing the effort and energy needed to shift the dial from the status quo in complex organisations. Projects specific to increasing thrombolysis use through the use of multicomponent interventions addressing barriers to use have proved disappointingly modest in their effects³³. Given how little we have seen the overall thrombolysis rate in England, Wales and Northern Ireland change over the last 10 years or more³⁴, it is quite apparent that substantial and sustained support is required to effect the sort of changes that this research indicates are potentially deliverable. Over that time the clinical community may have appeared rather too content to inhabit that ‘gap’ in delivery (the long-recognised ‘second gap of translation’ of the 2006 Cooksey Review³⁵), resulting in the long term failure to deliver to patients the fullest extent of the benefits from biomedical advances such as thrombolysis. What this work does, based as it is on real-world patients treated over recent years in the NHS, is highlight that there remains considerable health gain available simply through the more effective implementation of existing evidence - as much as a doubling of the population benefit - in parallel with the implementation of more recent advances in reperfusion for ischaemic stroke and in the management of haemorrhagic stroke. The complete implementation of treatments that we already know are highly effective and cost-effective is one of the principal means by which we shall reduce the huge burden on patients, their families and on wider society from the increasing prevalence of stroke-related disability around the world. This research shows that by identifying more eligible patients and delivering more thrombolysis to them more quickly, guided by realistic and bespoke modelled estimates of what is achievable and deliverable at each site, we could be confident that we will see less disability, better outcomes for our patients and reduced costs to society. The benefit that can be gained with this potentially relatively low resource implementation plan can be delivered in parallel with the more resource intensive implementation of newer treatments, such as thrombectomy. There can be no stronger argument for the fullest possible implementation of the available evidence.

10.3 Limitations

The limitations of this work need to be considered. The interpretation of observational data must always be balanced by an awareness of the potential pitfalls in the analysis of non-randomised data. In these studies these risks are significantly mitigated by the size of the dataset, and by the comprehensive, prospective nature of the national audit data – the inclusion of all sites in the UK (outside Scotland) which are regularly audited against expected case ascertainment from independent administrative/coding data, with an ascertainment of greater than 90%, is a safeguard against selection bias. The internal validations in the online case record forms used in SSNAP are also a safeguard against missing data and ensure at least 95% audit compliance, measures of completeness and data quality that have been maintained over 10 years in the audit. By the same token, it is often argued that observational datasets are more susceptible to incomplete adjustment for confounding, but the predictive power of the innovative machine learning methods in this study are demonstrated by the extremely close agreement between the observed and predicted hospital-specific thrombolysis rates, suggesting that no more than 5% of inter-hospital variation remains unaccounted for once all data are considered by the method. This would make it very unlikely that our observations about the sources of inter-hospital variation in thrombolysis are confounded by some unmeasured variable that is not included in SSNAP but is strongly predictive of the likelihood of thrombolysis – a theoretical variable that has thus far eluded identification despite being so strongly predictive. This work suggests that all-inclusive machine learning methods, using the computing power of massive

datasets to evaluate the contributions of a complete range of candidate variables, can offer much greater reassurance against incomplete adjustment than more traditional regression analyses.

Comparisons between outcomes from observational studies and randomised trials are similarly a matter of caution, and what is remarkable in this work is the degree of agreement between the expected benefits of thrombolysis predicted from the original trials and those predicted from analysis of this much larger dataset (over 11 times the size of the trials meta-analysis of Emberson et al.⁸) which incorporates a much wider range of eligible patients, particularly with reference to age and pre-stroke disability, who were on average treated much later after onset. This should provide ample reassurance to clinicians that in everyday practice they are conferring at least as much benefit to typical patients as in the more strictly defined and regulated circumstances of the trials from the early 1990s onwards. This observation holds despite the limitation of the current dataset to measurement of disability at hospital discharge, compared to at 90 days in the trials. Although it is known that the two are highly correlated after ischaemic stroke^{36;37}, significant proportions of patients do alter their disability status between the two time points (showing improvement and deterioration to similar extents³⁶) and this could introduce ‘noise’ into the analysis. This does not appear to alter the observed relationship, probably because discharge (or 30-day) disability is dominant in terms of predicting medium-term disability, accounting for over two-thirds of the observed variance in 90-day mRS in the Virtual International Stroke Trials Archive dataset³⁷.

The need to exclude patients who underwent mechanical thrombectomy from our analysis of outcomes may represent a potential limitation, necessary as it was in order to isolate the impact of thrombolysis alone from that of another highly effective reperfusion treatment. Ironically, the slow pace of adoption of thrombectomy particular to the UK has to a large extent insulated our analysis from this confounding effect. Over the time period of our dataset (2016-2021) the proportion of all stroke patients recorded as receiving thrombectomy in SSNAP rose slowly from 0.6% to 2.0%, and of course this group represent a highly selected cohort of severely impaired early-presenting patients, mostly with proximal middle cerebral artery occlusions and a median NIHSS of 16 (IQR 11-21; SSNAP Annual Thrombectomy Report 2020-21³⁸). The removal of these patients, approximately half of whom will also have received thrombolysis, may introduce selection bias, although this is likely to be in a conservative direction in terms of the efficacy of recanalisation. Their exclusion represents a conservative measure designed to enable analysis of the isolated effect of thrombolysis and thereby allow direct comparison with the original randomised trials of alteplase alone.

11 Patient and Public Involvement

Results have been regularly presented to a Patient and Carers Involvement (PCI) team. The PCI team has advised on both qualitative and quantitative research, and have helped shape communication of results.

In particular, the PCI have always advocated that it is outcomes, rather than any particular thrombolysis use target, that matters most. They also highlighted that modified Rankin Scale is an incomplete view of patient outcome, with particular omission of a measure of patients’ mental health or cognitive well-being. This has led to the development of a new funded project, working with the Stroke Data Science Catalyst (a partnership between the Stroke Association, the British Heart Foundation, and Health Data Research UK). This new project is looking at longer term outcomes from stroke, in the first instance focusing on days spent in care or at usual place of residence in the first 12 months after stroke.

The PCI team have also suggested, and will help with, further outputs from the SAMueL project. This will include short videos (e.g. for YouTube) and articles for relevant publications such as the Stroke Association’s *Stroke News* magazine.

12 Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI)

Although EDI was not a focus of this particular project’s objectives, to build substantial EDI into future work, we have performed the ground work required to link analysis of stroke treatment and outcomes to population demographics for each stroke team. We have combined data from multiple sources (at Lower Super Output Area, LSOA) and collated according to stroke team catchment areas (estimated by assigning each LSOA to the stroke team with the shortest travel time), and other areas such as Integrated Stroke Delivery Networks, and ambulance trust.

Data (source data and combined data) and code for this is available at: <https://github.com/samuel-book/stroke>

Figure 13: Screenshot from a page of our current web application on improving thrombolysis use.

`_unit_demographics`. Analysis is also made available by a web application at: https://stroke-unit-demographics.streamlit.app/Interactive_demo.

13 Impact and Learning

The following sections show how this work is already being used and adopted.

13.1 Production and demonstration code, with artificial patient data

Core analysis from this project is being implemented by SSNAP. This will give each team a bespoke thrombolysis target, based on their own local patient populations. For this, code, with artificial patient data, has been made available at https://github.com/samuel-book/samuel_2_demo. Artificial data made available is produced by sampling patient attributes separately from distributions based on real patient data attending each stroke team (with rounding/censoring process times and ages); covariances between sampled features are not maintained. This method may sometimes combine combinations of patient features that are not realistic of real patients. For machine learning data, the use of thrombolysis and the outcome data was generated by machine learning models predicting use of thrombolysis and outcome for that individual artificial patient. This data allows demonstration of the models, maintain many of the relationships between patient characteristics and use/outcome of thrombolysis, but should never be used for clinical research into stroke or for guidance on clinical decision-making.

13.2 SAMueL-2 Web Application

A web application has been made available to stroke teams at <https://stroke-predictions.streamlit.app/>. This web application allows teams to see descriptive statistics of all stroke teams, an analysis of the effect of potential pathway changes at each stroke team (using anonymised stroke team identity), and what thrombolysis decision each stroke team would make on a customisable patient (using anonymised stroke team identity). Figure 13 shows an example screenshot of potential thrombolysis use in one team, which could be potentially improved from 11.5% to 20.3%.

An example of feedback on presentation of the modelling available in the web app is shown below:

‘Dear Martin (James). I just wanted to drop you a Thank You email for visiting our Trust today [to present the stroke audit machine learning and modelling work] with your colleagues; your presentation was superb, so inspirational in terms of the difference we can make for the patients who are not currently receiving thrombolysis; a great illustration of how we compare in our decision making to the ‘premier’ hospitals.....I think this is amazing work with huge clinical benefit. If it helps, I’d be very happy to provide a letter of support on behalf of the Trust/ISDN’.

Ailsa Brotherton, Executive Director of Improvement, Research and Innovation, Improvement Director, National Improvement Board

13.3 Thrombolysis in Acute Stroke Collaborative (TASC)

The SAMueL team has been providing bespoke reports to the *Thrombolysis in Acute Stroke Collaborative (TASC)*. TASC is an NHS-England sponsored and funded project working with NHS Elect. TASC is taking 6 low thrombolysing stroke teams and is helping them improve thrombolysis use. A follow up project, focusing on 12-15 more teams has been agreed.

SAMueL has highlighted how decision-making in thrombolysis is a significant source of variation in thrombolysis. This has been recognised by stroke teams in the TASC project, and teams are engaging with with this challenge, but teams are left to work on their own solutions. As an example, one team now meet monthly to review thrombolysis ‘grey’ cases and they have also embraced a buddy “phone a friend” culture whereby any of them can phone another colleague to discuss thrombolysis decisions in more borderline cases.

13.4 Conference presentations

Work described here has been presented at the following conferences (presentations may be downloaded from the links provided):

Pearn, K., Allen, M., Laws, A., Everson, R. & James, M. (2023). What would other emergency stroke teams do? Using explainable machine learning to understand variation in thrombolysis practice. European Stroke Organisation Conference. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7878306>

Pearn, K., Allen, M., Laws, A., Everson, R. & James, M. (2023). What would other emergency stroke teams do? Using explainable machine learning to understand variation in thrombolysis (clot-busting) practice. AI UK 2023 (Turing Institute), London, UK. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7759059>

Pearn, K., Allen, M., Laws, A., & James, M. (2024). Variation in thrombolysis use and the potential effect on outcomes in england and wales: an observational machine learning study. European Stroke Organisation Conference (ESOC). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11191491>

Laws, A., Allen, M., Pearn, K., & James, M. (2024). Modelling disability-level and utility outcomes depending on time to thrombolysis and mechanical thrombectomy. European Stroke Organisation Conference (ESOC). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11191633>

14 Implications for decision makers

15 Research recommendations

Recommendations for further research include:

- How does variation in thrombolysis use (and resulting variation in outcomes) differ by population demographics?
- How does variation in thrombolysis use affect inpatient lengths of stay, and NHS bed use?
- How does use, benefit from, and bed use after, thrombectomy vary between admitting stroke team?
- Can causal inference methods (such as directed acyclic graphs, propensity score adjustment, and target trial emulation) confirm the conclusions made in this project?

- How do we maximise uptake and impact of this work?

16 Conclusions

We combined qualitative research and large-scale observational data with machine learning on use of, and outcomes from, thrombolysis. Both qualitative research and machine learning revealed significant between-hospital variation in which patients receive thrombolysis. Machine learning revealed that who will benefit from thrombolysis is patient-specific, and not easily captured in a simple medicine use label, but we found overall that stroke teams with a higher willingness to use thrombolysis are predicted to be generating better patient outcomes at a population level.

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18 Declaration of conflicting interests

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A1 Descriptive statistics

Tables A1 to A3 show descriptive statistics for patients (2016-2021) across all stroke teams for (1) all patients, patients arriving within 4 hours of known stroke onset, and patients arriving by ambulance within 4 hours of known stroke onset.

Table A1: Descriptive statistics for all patients (n = 360,381) arriving at each stroke team. The table shows summary statistics across all stroke teams capturing each feature.

Statistic	Stroke teams	mean	Std Dev	min	25%	50%	75%	max
Yearly admissions	119	509	208	95	372	489	627	1183
Age (mean)	119	74	2	65	73	75	76	78
Proportion aged 80+	119	0.40	0.06	0.20	0.36	0.40	0.44	0.51
Proportion male	119	0.53	0.02	0.47	0.51	0.53	0.55	0.60
Prior disability (mRS, mean)	119	1.02	0.25	0.29	0.87	1.03	1.21	1.60
Proportion prior disability (mRS) 0-2	119	0.81	0.05	0.67	0.78	0.81	0.84	0.97
Proportion ischaemic stroke	119	0.88	0.02	0.83	0.86	0.88	0.89	0.93
Stroke severity (NIHSS, mean)	119	7.0	1.0	4.6	6.3	7.2	7.8	9.1
Proportion with known onset	119	0.68	0.14	0.43	0.58	0.67	0.76	1.00
Onset-to-arrival time (minutes, median)	119	204	76	109	155	180	224	466
Proportion arriving within 4 hours known onset	119	0.38	0.06	0.19	0.34	0.38	0.43	0.51
Proportion with precisely known onset	119	0.33	0.11	0.01	0.28	0.34	0.39	0.63
Proportion onset during sleep	119	0.14	0.06	0.00	0.09	0.14	0.17	0.34
Proportion arrive by ambulance	119	0.78	0.07	0.47	0.76	0.79	0.82	0.92
Call-to-ambulance arrival time (minutes, median)	113	22	10	13	17	20	24	103
Ambulance on scene time (median)	113	31	3	20	28	31	33	41
Ambulance conveyance time (minutes, median)	113	18	5	10	15	17	21	37
Arrival-to-scan time (minutes, median)	119	53	21	13	39	51	63	129
Proportion receiving thrombolysis	119	0.115	0.034	0.021	0.092	0.110	0.136	0.245
Scan-to-thrombolysis time (minutes, median)	119	34	10	14	28	34	41	72
Discharge disability (mRS, mean)	119	2.641	0.352	1.361	2.413	2.699	2.900	3.320
Proportion discharged mRS 0-2	119	0.524	0.095	0.293	0.454	0.522	0.594	0.799
Proportion discharged mRS 5-6	119	0.195	0.037	0.095	0.170	0.198	0.218	0.287

Table A2: Descriptive statistics for patients (n = 138,946) arriving within 4 hours of known stroke onset at each stroke team. The table shows summary statistics across all stroke teams capturing each feature.

Statistic	Stroke teams	mean	Std Dev	min	25%	50%	75%	max
Yearly admissions	119	193	78	28	139	183	241	428
Age (mean)	119	75	2	66	73	75	76	79
Proportion aged 80+	119	0.41	0.06	0.23	0.37	0.41	0.45	0.57
Proportion male	119	0.53	0.03	0.45	0.51	0.53	0.55	0.64
Prior disability (mRS, mean)	119	1.04	0.25	0.37	0.88	1.04	1.22	1.60
Proportion prior disability (mRS) 0-2	119	0.80	0.06	0.66	0.77	0.81	0.83	0.95
Proportion ischaemic stroke	119	0.85	0.03	0.75	0.84	0.85	0.87	0.94
Stroke severity (NIHSS, mean)	119	8.9	1.1	6.4	8.2	9.0	9.7	11.4
Proportion with known onset	119	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Onset-to-arrival time (minutes, median)	119	105	9	85	100	105	111	132
Proportion arriving within 4 hours known onset	119	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Proportion with precisely known onset	119	0.62	0.17	0.02	0.54	0.66	0.75	0.91
Proportion onset during sleep	119	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.30
Proportion arrive by ambulance	119	0.89	0.07	0.54	0.87	0.91	0.93	0.98
Call-to-ambulance arrival time (minutes, median)	110	19	5	8	16	18	21	51
Ambulance on scene time (median)	110	28	4	20	26	28	31	46
Ambulance conveyance time (minutes, median)	110	17	4	9	14	16	20	28
Arrival-to-scan time (minutes, median)	119	27	11	4	21	28	34	100
Proportion receiving thrombolysis	119	0.293	0.070	0.111	0.250	0.282	0.333	0.534
Scan-to-thrombolysis time (minutes, median)	119	34	10	14	28	34	40	71
Discharge disability (mRS, mean)	119	2.803	0.353	1.507	2.609	2.837	3.039	3.663
Proportion discharged mRS 0-2	119	0.494	0.094	0.209	0.424	0.495	0.554	0.771
Proportion discharged mRS 5-6	119	0.236	0.045	0.138	0.208	0.231	0.256	0.420

Table A3: Descriptive statistics for patients (n = 125,557) arriving by ambulance within 4 hours of known stroke onset at each stroke team. The table shows summary statistics across all stroke teams capturing each feature.

Statistic	Stroke teams	mean	Std Dev	min	25%	50%	75%	max
Yearly admissions	119	173	74	15	125	163	227	400
Age (mean)	119	75	2	66	74	76	77	81
Proportion aged 80+	119	0.43	0.06	0.24	0.39	0.43	0.47	0.62
Proportion male	119	0.52	0.03	0.45	0.51	0.52	0.54	0.60
Prior disability (mRS, mean)	119	1.10	0.25	0.46	0.94	1.09	1.26	1.66
Proportion prior disability (mRS) 0-2	119	0.79	0.06	0.65	0.75	0.79	0.83	0.93
Proportion ischaemic stroke	119	0.85	0.03	0.75	0.83	0.85	0.87	0.94
Stroke severity (NIHSS, mean)	119	9.4	1.2	6.7	8.6	9.5	10.2	12.2
Proportion with known onset	119	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Onset-to-arrival time (minutes, median)	119	106	10	84	99	105	112	151
Proportion arriving within 4 hours known onset	119	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Proportion with precisely known onset	119	0.62	0.17	0.02	0.54	0.65	0.75	0.92
Proportion onset during sleep	119	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.33
Proportion arrive by ambulance	119	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Call-to-ambulance arrival time (minutes, median)	110	19	5	8	16	18	21	51
Ambulance on scene time (median)	110	28	4	20	26	28	31	46
Ambulance conveyance time (minutes, median)	110	17	4	9	14	16	20	28
Arrival-to-scan time (minutes, median)	119	26	11	4	20	25	33	95
Proportion receiving thrombolysis	119	0.300	0.072	0.130	0.252	0.289	0.345	0.537
Scan-to-thrombolysis time (minutes, median)	119	34	10	13	27	33	40	73
Discharge disability (mRS, mean)	119	2.926	0.352	1.867	2.717	2.928	3.150	3.819
Proportion discharged mRS 0-2	119	0.465	0.096	0.184	0.398	0.462	0.524	0.696
Proportion discharged mRS 5-6	119	0.254	0.051	0.147	0.221	0.253	0.280	0.486

A2 Review of objectives set in original bid

The following outlines the key objectives set out in the original bid, and what has been delivered:

A2.1 Objective 1: Expansion of SAMueL-1 modelling

Objective

Expansion of previous (SAMueL-1) modelling to include: 1) outcome and adverse event prediction at patient-level, 2) inclusion of pre-hospital times in pathway model, 3) use of organisational factors (such as staffing) in predicting use of thrombolysis, and 4) piloting of a model that incorporates use of thrombectomy alongside thrombolysis.

Project outputs

All objectives were achieved and reported:

- Outcome models are reported and used in sections 6, 7, and 8. Outcome and adverse event prediction at patient-level were predicted in the patient-level outcome model. We chose to use an all-cause beneficial/adverse outcome, rather than specific adverse events such as thrombolysis-induced haemorrhage. This was because we were primarily interested in net benefit or disbenefit from thrombolysis. Adverse outcomes associated with thrombolysis were taken as increased risk of severe death or disability (mRS 5-6). Outcome prediction was a very substantial part of this project, and included.
 - Development of models that predict probability of outcome across all disability (mRS) levels, and separate models to predict being within any given disability threshold on discharge.

- The addition of Shapley values (SHA) to outcome predictions, allow us to show, and analyse the contribution of individual features (such as use/time of thrombolysis) to patient outcomes.
- A comparison of the observed effect of thrombolysis (from our analysis) with clinical trial meta0analysis of thrombolysis.
- A comparison of who receives thrombolysis with who will benefit from thrombolysis (from our outcome models).
- Pre-hospital times (ambulance response and on-scene times) were included in the pathway model, and were used as a possible scenario for improvement (see section 8).
- We performed a multiple regression analysis on organisational factors from the SSNAP audit. We did not find any significant link to willingness to use thrombolysis (see 9).
- We performed a pilot model on the benefit from thrombectomy (and confirmed a beneficial effect that declines over time). The data set was small for this intervention and more work will be required to make this work suitable for publication (we have included pilot work in section 9 (*Other project outputs* as results should be considered indicative rather than at a level suitable for robust peer review.)

A2.2 Objective 2: Incorporation of health economic outcomes

Objective

Incorporation of health economic outcomes (Quality Adjusted Life Years, QALYs): These will be adapted from other NIHR projects involving this team that have already developed health economic models for thrombolysis in acute ischaemic stroke.

This objective was achieved and reported:

Project outputs

- A health economics model for stroke has been coded by the SAMueL team and is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/stroke-optimist/stroke-lifetime> and available for installation on Python from PyPI (<https://pypi.org/project/stroke-lifetime/>).
- The effect of thrombolysis on, life expectancy, QALYs, NHS care costs, and cost per QALY are included in section 8.

A2.3 Objective 3: Promote acceptance of the modelling by increased transparency and explainability

Objective

Promote acceptance of the modelling by increased transparency and explainability: 1) make use of Shapley values to show the contribution of individual features to the prediction that the model is making, 2) improved methods for clustering of patients to clarify patterns of differences in clinical decision-making between hospitals and to allow identification of ‘similar hospitals’ (by patient population) for comparison, 3) investigation of bias in model (e.g. accuracy analysis by patient subgroups), 4) generation of dashboards and other interrogative methods.

Project outputs

All objectives were achieved and reported, except we did not have the data to analyse model accuracy by key demographic groups (as we were concerned about possible identification of people by inclusion of ethnicity; though we have a plan for for for future work):

- Shapley values have been used extensively to explore the relationship between patient features and model predictions (thrombolysis use, and outcomes). These have been performed at patient and population level. See sections 5, 6, 7.

- We identified key characteristics of patients where stroke teams make different decisions and condensed these into prototype patients. This allowed us to identify stroke teams that were, for example, less likely to give thrombolysis to patients with mild stroke, pre-stroke disability or with imprecisely known stroke onset times. See sections 5 and 8.
- Shapely values help reveal 'bias' in the model by showing how patient features affect model predictions. We did not analyse accuracy by subgroup. In our final data request we did not include ethnicity as we had some concern about identification of patients in small minority groups. In future work we will ask for 2-3 ethnic groups and include others as 'other' and we will reduce the granularity of other data (such as month of attendance) to avoid possible identification. This will allow us to perform an analysis of thrombolysis use and outcomes, and model accuracy by ethnicity. We will also access decile of Index of Multiple Deprivation to perform similar analysis by this index.
- Our models have been made available as web app dashboard: <https://stroke-predictions.streamlit.app/>. At this stage we have not included patient-level outcome predictions due to a concern that it could be used for clinical decision-making.

A2.4 Objective 4: Generation of synthetic data and artificial patient vignettes

Objective

Generation of synthetic data and artificial patient vignettes: 1) build on pilot work already performed for generating synthetic patient-level stroke data that may be shared freely and used for discussion of 'virtual' patients, 2) automatic generation of artificial clinical vignettes from real or synthetic SSNAP data.

Project outputs

These objectives were achieved, but in a slightly different way to planned:

- We were able to make artificial patient data by crudely sampling key patient characteristics, but then allocating thrombolysis use and outcomes based on model predictions based on real patients. These data are made available in the project code demonstration GitHub repository: <https://stroke-predictions.streamlit.app/>.
- As we simplified models to as few patient features as necessary for good predictions we are able to describe patients succinctly. We also developed *prototype patients* that could be used to compare outcomes (see section 8).

A2.5 Objective 5: Co-production of project outputs with clinicians to promote acceptance and use for local quality improvement

Original objective:

Co-production of project outputs with clinicians to promote acceptance and use for local quality improvement: By using both information gathering (through interviews) and intervention refinement (in workshops) we will incrementally modify and improve the content and style of our intervention (SAMueL tool). Working with our Public and Patient Involvement (PPI) group we will also produce key public-facing output.

Amended objective

With agreement of NIHR (through a *Variation to Contract* agreement) the qualitative approach was altered to:

What should a machine-learning model based on SSNAP data look like, do, and deliver if it is to optimise improvement, and reduce unwarranted variation, in thrombolysis?

1. To generate empirically and theoretically informed knowledge about how thrombolysis is currently delivered, centred on physicians' views, understandings, and practices.
2. To learn more about how stroke physicians' and staff think and feel about or use SSNAP, and about the use of machine learning in improving clinical practice.

Project outputs

All objectives of the revised objectives were met (section 4).

Using the NASS framework we identified three learning points which, if addressed, may facilitate further implementation of the technology.

- Given reservations expressed by some of our participants and healthcare professionals elsewhere about the underpinning SSNAP data it seems important to ensure that intended adopters are reassured about the integrity of modelling based on this data.
- Evidence from this research and elsewhere indicates that the ED physicians' may have less confidence in the evidence base for, and safety of thrombolysis. It is therefore likely that more work will need to be done with the ED physician community to build trust in the SAMuel-2 technology: recruiting ED physicians as brokers/clinical champions may help to address this.
- Perceived lack of funding/resource and stroke workforce shortages may impede quality improvement and adoption of new technologies such as SAMueL-2.